

Permutation polynomials $(x^{p^m} - x + \delta)^{s_1} + (x^{p^m} - x + \delta)^{s_2} + x$ over $\mathbb{F}_{p^n}$

Lisha Li *, Shi Wang, Chaoyun Li†, Xiangyong Zeng

Abstract: In this paper, we propose several classes of permutation polynomials with the form $(x^{p^m} - x + \delta)^{s_1} + (x^{p^m} - x + \delta)^{s_2} + x$ over finite fields. The permutation behavior of the proposed polynomials is investigated by the AGW criterion and determination of the number of solutions to certain equations over finite fields.

Keywords: Finite field, permutation polynomial, trace function, AGW criterion

MSC: 05A05, 11T06, 11T55

1 Introduction

Let $\mathbb{F}_q$ be a finite field of q elements, where q is a prime power. A polynomial $f \in \mathbb{F}_q[x]$ is called a *permutation polynomial* (PP) if its associated polynomial mapping $f: c \mapsto f(c)$ from $\mathbb{F}_q$ to itself is a bijection. Permutation polynomials over finite fields play important roles in cryptography, coding theory and combinatorial design theory [5].

In 2003, new Kloosterman sums identities over $\mathbb{F}_{2^n}$ were established by applying PPs of the form

$$\left(\frac{1}{x^2 - x + \delta}\right)^{2^l} + x,$$

where $\delta \in \mathbb{F}_{2^n}$ and $l = 0, 1$ [3]. This led Yuan and Ding to investigate the PPs of the form

$$\left(x^{p^i} - x + \delta\right)^s + L(x) \tag{1}$$

*L. Li, S. Wang and X. Zeng (Corresponding author) are with the Faculty of Mathematics and Statistics, Hubei Key Laboratory of applied mathematics, Hubei University, Wuhan 430062, China. X. Zeng is also with State Key Laboratory of Information Security, Institute of Information Engineering, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Beijing 100093, China. Email: xiangyongzeng@aliyun.com.

†C. Li is with imec-COSIC, Department of Electrical Engineering, KU Leuven, Leuven 3001, Belgium. Email: chaoyun.li@esat.kuleuven.be.

over $\mathbb{F}_{p^n}$, where p is a prime, i, n, s are positive integers, $\delta \in \mathbb{F}_{p^n}$, and $L(x)$ is a linearized polynomial with coefficients in $\mathbb{F}_p$ [9, 10]. After the pioneering works, a series of papers [4, 6–8, 11–15, 17, 18] treated the same topic of specifying new classes of permutation polynomials with the form as in (1). Very recently, eight classes of PPs with the form

$$\left(x^{2^i} + x + \delta\right)^{s_1} + \left(x^{2^i} + x + \delta\right)^{s_2} + x$$

over finite fields of characteristic 2 were presented in [16], where i, n, s_1, s_2 are positive integers and $\delta \in \mathbb{F}_{2^n}$.

The purpose of this paper is to propose new classes of PPs with the form

$$f(x) = (x^{p^m} - x + \delta)^{s_1} + (x^{p^m} - x + \delta)^{s_2} + x \quad (2)$$

over $\mathbb{F}_{p^n}$, where p is a prime, m, n, s_1, s_2 are positive integers with $m | n$ and $\delta \in \mathbb{F}_{p^n}$. We investigate PPs of the form (2) in two main ways. One is to construct new PPs $f(x)$ from the known PPs of the form $(x^{p^m} - x + \delta)^s + x$. In this way, a large number of new PPs of the form (2) over $\mathbb{F}_{p^n}$ can be obtained. Moreover, we construct new PPs with the form $(x^{p^m} - x + \delta)^s + x$, which can be used to construct new PPs over $\mathbb{F}_{p^n}$ with the form (2). The other is to construct new PPs $f(x)$ in terms of the relationship $s_2 \equiv p^t s_1 \pmod{p^m - 1}$ between the exponents s_1 and s_2 , where t is an integer. In addition, some other PPs having the form as in (2) are also constructed. The main proofs in this paper depend on the AGW criterion (see Lemma 2 in Section 2), which reduces the problem of proving PPs over $\mathbb{F}_{p^n}$ to that of proving PPs over its subgroup. By Lemma 2 and the properties of the trace function, the permutation problem is further transformed into determining the number of solutions to a related linear or quadratic equation over $\mathbb{F}_{p^n}$.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, we introduce some basic concepts and related results. New permutation polynomials having the form as in (2) are proposed in Sections 3, 4 and 5.

2 Preliminaries

Let m and n be two positive integers with $m | n$. The trace function $\text{Tr}_m^n(\cdot)$ from $\mathbb{F}_{p^n}$ to $\mathbb{F}_{p^m}$ is defined by

$$\text{Tr}_m^n(x) = x + x^{p^m} + x^{p^{2m}} + \cdots + x^{p^{(n/m-1)m}}, \quad x \in \mathbb{F}_{p^n}.$$

Define a subset of $\mathbb{F}_{p^n}$ by

$$\mathcal{J} = \{\gamma^{p^m} - \gamma \mid \gamma \in \mathbb{F}_{p^n}\}. \quad (3)$$

Then for any element $\beta \in \mathcal{J}$, we have

$$\mathrm{Tr}_m^n(\beta) = 0. \quad (4)$$

Let q be a prime power. If $\varphi(x) = \sum_{j=0}^s \alpha_j x^{q^j}$ with coefficients in $\mathbb{F}_q$, then we called $\varphi(x)$ an $\mathbb{F}_q$ -linear polynomial over $\mathbb{F}_q$ [1].

We recall a result followed from the AGW criterion [1].

Lemma 1 ([1]). *For positive integers m, n with $m \mid n$, let $\varphi(x)$ be an $\mathbb{F}_{p^m}$ -linear polynomial over $\mathbb{F}_{p^m}$, $h(x) \in \mathbb{F}_{p^n}[x]$ be a polynomial such that $h(x^{p^m} - x) \in \mathbb{F}_{p^m} \setminus \{0\}$ for all $x \in \mathbb{F}_{p^n}$, and $g(x) \in \mathbb{F}_{p^n}[x]$ be any polynomial. Then $h(x^{p^m} - x)\varphi(x) + g(x^{p^m} - x)$ is a permutation of $\mathbb{F}_{p^n}$ if and only if*

- (i) $\varphi(x)$ induces a permutation polynomial of $\mathbb{F}_{p^m}$;
- (ii) $h(x)\varphi(x) + g(x)^{p^m} - g(x)$ permutes $\mathcal{J}$ defined in (3).

The following result can be immediately obtained by taking $h(x) = 1$, $\varphi(x) = x$ and $g(x) = \sum_{j=1}^t (x + \delta)^{s_j}$ in Lemma 1.

Lemma 2. *For given positive integers m, n, t with $m \mid n$, nonnegative integers s_j for $1 \leq j \leq t$, and a fixed $\delta \in \mathbb{F}_{p^n}$, the polynomial*

$$f(x) = \sum_{j=1}^t (x^{p^m} - x + \delta)^{s_j} + x$$

permutes $\mathbb{F}_{p^n}$ if and only if $\sum_{j=1}^t ((x + \delta)^{p^m s_j} - (x + \delta)^{s_j}) + x$ permutes $\mathcal{J}$.

The following result will be frequently used to determine the number of solutions to some linearized polynomials.

Lemma 3. *Let p be a prime, two positive integers m and n satisfy $mp \nmid n$ and $m \mid n$, and two nonnegative integers i, j satisfy $\gcd(i - j, n) = 1$ and $\gcd(i - j, p - 1) = 1$. If the element $\alpha \in \mathbb{F}_{p^n}$ is a $(p - 1)$ -th power in $\mathbb{F}_{p^m}$, then the equation $x^{p^i} - \alpha x^{p^j} + \beta = 0$ has at most one solution in $\mathcal{J}$ defined by (3), where $\beta \in \mathbb{F}_{p^n}$.*

Proof. Since $x^{p^i} - \alpha x^{p^j} + \beta$ is an affine polynomial over $\mathbb{F}_{p^n}$, it suffices to prove that the equation

$$x^{p^i} - \alpha x^{p^j} = 0$$

has the unique solution 0 in $\mathcal{J}$.

The conclusion is true for $\alpha = 0$. For the case $\alpha \neq 0$, to finish the proof, it suffices to prove that

$$x^{p^j(p^{i-j}-1)} = \alpha \quad (5)$$

has no solution in $\mathcal{J}$.

Assume that x_0 is a root of (5), then $x_0^{p^j(p^{i-j}-1)} = \alpha$. Since α is a $(p-1)$ -th power in $\mathbb{F}_{p^m}^*$, there exists an element $\gamma \in \mathbb{F}_{p^m}^*$ such that $\alpha = \gamma^{p-1} = x_0^{p^j(p^{i-j}-1)}$. Thus

$$x_0^{\frac{p^j(p^{i-j}-1)}{p-1}} = \eta\gamma = (\eta\gamma)^{p^m} = x_0^{\frac{p^{j+m}(p^{i-j}-1)}{p-1}}, \quad (6)$$

where $\eta \in \mathbb{F}_p^*$. Since $\gcd(i-j, n) = 1$, we have $\gcd(p^{i-j}-1, p^n-1) = p-1$ and then $\gcd\left(\frac{p^{i-j}-1}{p-1}, \frac{p^n-1}{p-1}\right) = 1$. Note that $\frac{p^{i-j}-1}{p-1} = (p^{i-j-1}-1) + (p^{i-j-2}-1) + \dots + (p-1) + i-j$ and $p-1 \mid p^k-1$ for any $k \geq 1$. Hence $\gcd\left(\frac{p^{i-j}-1}{p-1}, p-1\right) = \gcd(i-j, p-1)$. This implies $\gcd\left(\frac{p^{i-j}-1}{p-1}, p-1\right) = 1$ since $\gcd(i-j, p-1) = 1$. Consequently, we have

$$\gcd\left(\frac{p^j(p^{i-j}-1)}{p-1}, p^n-1\right) = \gcd\left(\frac{p^{i-j}-1}{p-1}, p^n-1\right) = 1$$

due to the fact

$$\gcd\left(\frac{p^{i-j}-1}{p-1}, p^n-1\right) \mid \gcd\left(\frac{p^{i-j}-1}{p-1}, p-1\right) \cdot \gcd\left(\frac{p^{i-j}-1}{p-1}, \frac{p^n-1}{p-1}\right).$$

Then by (6), $x_0^{p^m} = x_0$. Therefore, $\text{Tr}_m^n(x_0) = \frac{n}{m} \cdot x_0 \neq 0$ due to $mp \nmid n$, which contradicts the fact that $x_0 \in \mathcal{J}$. Thus (5) has no solution in $\mathcal{J}$. This completes the proof. $\square$

3 PPs $f(x)$ from permutations $(x^{p^m} - x + \delta)^s + x$ over $\mathbb{F}_{p^n}$

In this section, we study a class of polynomials having the form as in (2) over $\mathbb{F}_{p^n}$, whose permutation behavior can be characterized by the polynomials having the form as in (1). Some new PPs of the form $(x^{p^m} - x + \delta)^s + x$ are also proposed.

Theorem 1. *For positive integers m, n, j, s with $m \mid n$, and a fixed $\delta \in \mathbb{F}_{p^n}$, the polynomial*

$$f(x) = (x^{p^m} - x + \delta)^{\frac{j(p^n-1)}{p^m-1}} + (x^{p^m} - x + \delta)^s + x \quad (7)$$

permutes $\mathbb{F}_{p^n}$ if and only if

$$h(x) = (x^{p^m} - x + \delta)^s + x$$

permutes $\mathbb{F}_{p^n}$.

Proof. By Lemma 2, $f(x)$ is a permutation of $\mathbb{F}_{p^n}$ if and only if

$$\begin{aligned} & (x + \delta)^{\frac{p^m j(p^n - 1)}{p^m - 1}} - (x + \delta)^{\frac{j(p^n - 1)}{p^m - 1}} + (x + \delta)^{p^m s} - (x + \delta)^s + x \\ = & (x + \delta)^{j(p^n - 1) + \frac{j(p^n - 1)}{p^m - 1}} - (x + \delta)^{\frac{j(p^n - 1)}{p^m - 1}} + (x + \delta)^{p^m s} - (x + \delta)^s + x \\ = & (x + \delta)^{p^m s} - (x + \delta)^s + x \end{aligned}$$

is a permutation of $\mathcal{J}$ defined by (3). Again by Lemma 2, $h(x)$ is a permutation of $\mathbb{F}_{p^n}$ if and only if

$$(x + \delta)^{p^m s} - (x + \delta)^s + x$$

is a permutation of $\mathcal{J}$. Hence $f(x)$ permutes $\mathbb{F}_{p^n}$ if and only if $h(x)$ permutes $\mathbb{F}_{p^n}$. $\square$

Remark 1. (1) If $s = 0$ and $\delta \notin \mathcal{J}$, then similarly to Theorem 1 one can prove that the polynomial

$$f(x) = (x^{p^m} - x + \delta)^{\frac{j(p^n - 1)}{p^m - 1}} + x + 1$$

is a permutation of $\mathbb{F}_{p^n}$ where m, n, j are nonnegative integers with $m \mid n$ and $m, n > 0$. It follows that

$$(x^{p^m} - x + \delta)^{\frac{j(p^n - 1)}{p^m - 1}} + x$$

permutes $\mathbb{F}_{p^n}$, which is a special case of the Corollary 6.3 in [11].

(2) In Theorem 1, we have

$$\frac{j(p^n - 1)}{p^m - 1} = \begin{cases} j(p^m + 1), & \text{if } n = 2m; \\ j(p^{2m} + p^m + 1), & \text{if } n = 3m. \end{cases}$$

Note that in Theorem 3 of [16], the case for $s_1 = 2^m + 1$ and $s_2 = 2^{m+1} - 1$ in (2) was investigated by considering the number of solutions to a cubic equation over $\mathbb{F}_{2^{2m}}$. This can be easily obtained by Theorem 1 and the permutation property of $(x^{2^m} + x + \delta)^{2^{m+1} - 1} + x$ over $\mathbb{F}_{2^{2m}}$ [6]. Moreover, the range of s_1 can be extended to $s_1 = j(2^m + 1)$ for an arbitrary nonnegative integer j .

Based on Theorem 1, a large number of PPs of the form (7) can be obtained from PPs of the form $(x^{p^m} - x + \delta)^s + x$. Some known permutation polynomials $(x^{p^m} - x + \delta)^s + x$ over $\mathbb{F}_{p^n}$ are listed in Tables 1 and 2, where $n = 2m$ or $n = 3m$.

In the sequel, some new permutation polynomials of the form $f(x) = (x^{p^m} - x + \delta)^s + x$ over $\mathbb{F}_{p^n}$ are proposed. With Theorem 1, new permutation polynomials of the form as in (7) are then obtained.

Proposition 1. For a positive integer m and a fixed $\delta \in \mathbb{F}_{p^{2m}}$, the polynomial

$$f(x) = (x^{p^m} - x + \delta)^{2p^m} + x$$

is a permutation of $\mathbb{F}_{p^{2m}}$ if and only if $2\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta) + 1 \neq 0$.

Table 1: Some permutation polynomials $(x^{2^m} + x + \delta)^s + x$ over $\mathbb{F}_{2^n}$

Values of m, n and s	Conditions on δ	Reference
$n = 2m, m = 1$ and $s = -2$	$\delta^2 + \delta = 1$	[9]
$n = 2m, m = 2$ and $s = -2$	$\text{Tr}_1^4(\delta) = 1$	[10]
$n = 2m, s(2^m - 1) \equiv 0 \pmod{2^{2m} - 1}$	all	[11]
$n = 2m$, all s, m	$\delta \in \mathbb{F}_{2^m}$	[12]
$n = 2m, s = 2^{m+1} - 1$	all	[6]
$n = 2m, s = 2^{m+1} + 3$	$\delta \in \mathbb{F}_{2^m}$ or $\delta \notin \mathbb{F}_{2^m}$ with $\text{Tr}_1^{2m}(\delta) = \text{Tr}_1^m(1)$ and $p_m((\delta + \delta^{2^m})^{-1}) \neq 0$ $p_1(x) = p_2(x) = 1$ $p_k = p_{k-1} + x^{2^{k-3}}$ for $k \geq 3$	[6]
$n = 2m, s \in \{2^m + 2, 2^{2m} - 2^m - 1, 2^{2m-1} + 2^{m-1} + 1\}$	$\delta \in \mathbb{F}_{2^m}$ or $\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta) = 1$	[6]
$n = 2m, m \not\equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ and $s = 3 \cdot 2^{2m-2} + 2^{m-2}$	all	[18]
$n = 2m, m$ is even and $s = (2^{2m} + 2^m + 1)/3$	all	[18]
$n = 2m, s = 2^{2m-2} + 2^{m-2} + 1$	$\delta \in \mathbb{F}_{2^m}$ or $\delta \notin \mathbb{F}_{2^m}$ with $\text{Tr}_1^{2m}(\delta) = \text{Tr}_1^m(1)$ and $p_m((\delta + \delta^{2^m})^{-1}) \neq 0$ $p_1(x) = p_2(x) = 1$ $p_k = p_{k-1} + x^{2^{k-3}}$ for $k \geq 3$	[18]
$n = 2m, s = 2^i$	all	[2]
$n = 2m, m \not\equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ and $s = 2^{2m-2} + 3 \cdot 2^{m-2}$	all	[8]
$n = 2m, s \in \{2^{2m-1} + 2^{m-1}, 2^{2m} - 2^m + 1\}$	all	[8]
$n = 2m, m$ is even and $s = (2^{2m+1} + 2^{m+1} - 1)/3$	all	[8]
$n = 3m, m, n$ are even, $s(2^m - 1) \equiv 0 \pmod{2^{\frac{n}{2}} - 1}$	$\text{Tr}_1^{3m}(\delta) = 1$	[15]
$n = 3m, s(2^m - 1) \equiv 0 \pmod{2^n - 1}$	all	[15]
$n = 3m, s = 2^{2m} + 1$	all	This paper
$n = 3m, s = 2^{im-1} + 2^{m-1}, \gcd((i-1)m - 1, 3m) = 1, i \in \{2, 3\}$	all	This paper

Proof. By Lemma 2, to prove that $f(x)$ permutes $\mathbb{F}_{p^{2m}}$, it suffices to prove that for any $d \in \mathcal{J}$, the equation

$$(x + \delta)^{p^m(2p^m)} - (x + \delta)^{2p^m} + x = d$$

has exactly one solution in $\mathcal{J}$. Note that $x^{p^m} = -x$ for $x \in \mathcal{J}$. Then the left hand of the above equality becomes

$$\begin{aligned} & (x + \delta)^{p^m(2p^m)} - (x + \delta)^{2p^m} + x \\ &= (x + \delta)^2 - (-x + \delta^{p^m})^2 + x \\ &= (x^2 + 2\delta x + \delta^2) - (x^2 - 2\delta^{p^m} x + \delta^{2p^m}) + x \\ &= (2\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta) + 1)x - (\delta^{2p^m} - \delta^2), \end{aligned}$$

and we have

$$(2\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta) + 1)x = \delta^{2p^m} - \delta^2 + d. \quad (8)$$

If $2\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta) + 1 \neq 0$, then $x = \frac{\delta^{2p^m} - \delta^2 + d}{2\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta) + 1}$ is the unique solution of (8) in $\mathcal{J}$ due to $\text{Tr}_m^{2m} \left(\frac{\delta^{2p^m} - \delta^2 + d}{2\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta) + 1} \right) = 0$.

Table 2: Some permutation polynomials $(x^{p^m} - x + \delta)^s + x$ over $\mathbb{F}_{p^n}$ with odd prime p

Values of p, m, n and s	Conditions on δ	Reference
$n = 2m, p = 3, m = 1$ and $s = -1$	$\text{Tr}_1^2(\delta) \neq 0$	[10]
$n = 2m, s(p^m - 1) \equiv 0 \pmod{p^{2m} - 1}$	all	[11]
$n = 2m, s$ even	$\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta) = 0$	[12]
$n = 2m, s = \frac{p^{2m}-1}{d} + 1, d \in \{2, 3, 4, 6\}$, and the details of the parameters p and m are mentioned in [13]	$\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta) = 0$	[13]
$n = 2m, p^m \equiv 2 \pmod{3}, s = \frac{p^{2m}-1}{3} + 1$ and $-\frac{1}{2}$ is a cube of $\mathbb{F}_{p^{2m}}^*$	$\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta) = 0$	[4]
$n = 2m, p \neq 7, p^m \equiv 1 \pmod{3}, s = \frac{p^{2m}-1}{3} + 1, \frac{\alpha(2\gamma^2-1)}{2\gamma-1}$ is not a cube in $\mathbb{F}_{p^{2m}}^*$, where $\gamma = \alpha^{\frac{p^{2m}-1}{3}}$ and α is a primitive element of $\mathbb{F}_{p^{2m}}^*$	$\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta) = 0$	[4]
$n = 2m, p = 3, s = 3^m + 2$	$(\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta))^2 + 1 = 0$ or a square of $\mathbb{F}_{3^m}$	[7]
$n = 2m, p = 3, m$ even, $s = 3^{2m} - 3^m - 1$	$(\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta))^2 + 1 = 0$	[7]
$n = 2m, s = i(p^m - 1) + 1, 0 < i < p^m$, and i is even if $p = 3$	$\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta) = 0$	[7]
$n = 2m, p = 3, s = 2 \cdot 3^{2m-1} + 3^{m-1}$	$\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta) \neq 0$	[17]
$n = 2m, s = i(3^m - 1) + 1, i \equiv -3^{m-1} \pmod{3^m + 1}$	$\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta) \neq 0$	[14]
$n = 2m, s = 2p^m$	$2\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta) + 1 \neq 0$	This paper
$n = 2m, s = p^{m+1} + 1$	$\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta) = 0$ or $\frac{\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta)-1}{\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta)}$ is a $(p-1)$ -th power in $\mathbb{F}_{p^m}$	This paper
$n = 3m, s(p^m - 1) \equiv 0 \pmod{p^{3m} - 1}$	all	[11]
$n = 3m, p = 3$ and $s = 2^{\frac{3^n-1}{2}} + 3^{im}, i = 0, 1, 2$	$\text{Tr}_m^{3m}(\delta) = 0$	[17]
$n = 3m, s = \frac{p^n-1}{2} + p^m, k$ is an integer	all	[4]
$n = 2m, p = 3, s = 3^{2m-1} + 2 \cdot 3^{m-1}$	all	This paper

If $f(x)$ is a permutation of $\mathbb{F}_{p^{2m}}$, by Lemma 2 Equation (8) has exactly one solution in $\mathcal{J}$ for each $d \in \mathcal{J}$. This shows $2\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta) + 1 \neq 0$. $\square$

In Proposition 1, for the case $p = 2, f(x) = (x^{2^m} - x + \delta)^{2^{m+1}} + x$ is a linearized polynomial that permutes $\mathbb{F}_{2^{2m}}$ since $2\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta) + 1 = 1 \neq 0$ holds for each $\delta \in \mathbb{F}_{2^{2m}}$.

Proposition 2. *For an odd prime p and a positive integer m , let δ be an element of $\mathbb{F}_{p^{2m}}$ such that $\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta) = 0$ or $\frac{\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta)-1}{\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta)}$ is a $(p-1)$ -th power in $\mathbb{F}_{p^m}$, then the polynomial*

$$f(x) = (x^{p^m} - x + \delta)^{p^{m+1}+1} + x$$

is a permutation of $\mathbb{F}_{p^{2m}}$.

Proof. By Lemma 2, it suffices to prove that for each $d \in \mathcal{J}$, the equation

$$(x + \delta)^{p^{m+p}} - (x + \delta)^{p^{m+1}+1} + x = d$$

has at most one solution in $\mathcal{J}$. Since $x^{p^m} = -x$ for $x \in \mathcal{J}$, the left hand of the above equality can be rewritten as

$$\begin{aligned} & (x + \delta)^{p^{m+p}} - (x + \delta)^{p^{m+1}+1} + x \\ &= (-x + \delta^{p^m})(x^p + \delta^p) - (-x^p + \delta^{p^{m+1}})(x + \delta) + x \\ &= (-x^{p+1} + \delta^{p^m}x^p - \delta^p x + \delta^{p^{m+p}}) - (-x^{p+1} - \delta x^p + \delta^{p^{m+1}}x + \delta^{p^{m+1}+1}) + x \\ &= (\delta^{p^m} + \delta)x^p - (\delta^{p^m} + \delta - 1)^p x + \delta^{p^{m+p}} - \delta^{p^{m+1}+1} \\ &= \text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta)x^p - (\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta) - 1)^p x + \delta^{p^{m+p}} - \delta^{p^{m+1}+1}. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, we have

$$\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta)x^p - (\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta) - 1)^p x = \delta^{p^{m+1}+1} - \delta^{p^{m+p}} + d. \quad (9)$$

When $\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta) = 0$, $\delta^{p^{m+1}+1} - \delta^{p^{m+p}} = (-\delta)^p \delta - \delta^p(-\delta) = 0$ and then $x = d$ is the unique solution of (9). When $\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta) \neq 0$, (9) becomes

$$x^p - \frac{(\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta) - 1)^p}{\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta)} x = \frac{\delta^{p^{m+1}+1} - \delta^{p^{m+p}} + d}{\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta)}. \quad (10)$$

Note that $\frac{\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta) - 1}{\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta)}$ is a $(p-1)$ -th power in $\mathbb{F}_{p^m}$, then there exists $\gamma_0 \in \mathbb{F}_{p^m}$ such that

$$\frac{(\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta) - 1)^p}{\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta)} = \gamma_0^{p-1} (\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta) - 1)^{p-1} = (\gamma_0 \text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta) - \gamma_0)^{p-1}.$$

Moreover, $mp \nmid 2m$ due to that p is an odd prime. Thus, (10) has at most one solution in $\mathcal{J}$ by Lemma 3. That is to say, (9) has at most one solution in $\mathcal{J}$ and the proof is finished. $\square$

Example 1. (1) Take $m = 2$ and $p = 3$. By computer, there are 36 different $\delta \in \mathbb{F}_{3^4}$ such that $\frac{\text{Tr}_2^4(\delta) - 1}{\text{Tr}_2^4(\delta)}$ is a square element in $\mathbb{F}_{3^2}$ and 9 different $\delta \in \mathbb{F}_{3^4}$ satisfying $\text{Tr}_2^4(\delta) = 0$, and these δ are exactly all the elements in $\mathbb{F}_{3^4}$ such that

$$f(x) = (x^9 - x + \delta)^{28} + x$$

is a permutation of $\mathbb{F}_{3^4}$. Moreover, it is verified that the polynomial $f(x)$ is not a permutation when $\frac{\text{Tr}_2^4(\delta) - 1}{\text{Tr}_2^4(\delta)}$ is not a square element in $\mathbb{F}_{3^2}$. In this example, all possible elements $\delta \in \mathbb{F}_{3^4}$ such that $f(x)$ is a permutation over $\mathbb{F}_{3^4}$ are covered by Proposition 2, and the condition on δ in Proposition 2 is sharp.

(2) Take $m = 3$, $p = 2$ and $\delta = \omega$, where ω is a root of the primitive polynomial $x^6 + x + 1$. By computer, it can be verified that

$$f(x) = (x^8 - x + \omega)^{17} + x$$

is not a permutation of $\mathbb{F}_{2^6}$. That shows the result of Proposition 2 does not hold any longer for $p = 2$.

Proposition 3. For an even positive integer m and a fixed $\delta \in \mathbb{F}_{3^{2m}}$, the polynomial

$$f(x) = (x^{3^m} - x + \delta)^{3^{2m-1}+2 \cdot 3^{m-1}} + x$$

is a permutation of $\mathbb{F}_{3^{2m}}$.

Proof. By Lemma 2, it suffices to prove that for any $d \in \mathcal{J}$, the equation

$$(x + \delta)^{3^{m-1}+2 \cdot 3^{2m-1}} - (x + \delta)^{3^{2m-1}+2 \cdot 3^{m-1}} + x = d \quad (11)$$

has at most one solution in $\mathcal{J}$. Raising both sides of (11) to the power 3, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & (x + \delta)^{3^{m+2}} - (x + \delta)^{2 \cdot 3^{m+1}} + x^3 \\ = & (-x + \delta^{3^m})(x + \delta)^2 - (x - \delta^{3^m})^2(x + \delta) + x^3 \\ = & (-x + \delta^{3^m})(x^2 - \delta x + \delta^2) - (x^2 + \delta^{3^m}x + \delta^{2 \cdot 3^m})(x + \delta) + x^3 \\ = & -x^3 + (\delta^{3^m} + \delta)x^2 - (\delta^2 + \delta^{3^m+1})x + \delta^{3^m+2} - (x^3 + (\delta^{3^m} + \delta)x^2 + \\ & (\delta^{2 \cdot 3^m} + \delta^{3^m+1})x + \delta^{2 \cdot 3^m+1}) + x^3 \\ = & -x^3 - (\delta^{3^m} + \delta)^2x + \delta^{3^m+2} - \delta^{2 \cdot 3^m+1} \\ = & d^3 \end{aligned}$$

and then

$$x^3 + [\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta)]^2x = \delta^{3^m+2} - \delta^{2 \cdot 3^m+1} - d^3. \quad (12)$$

Denote by α a primitive element of $\mathbb{F}_{3^m}$. Since m is even, $4 \mid 3^m - 1$ and $-1 = \alpha^{\frac{3^m-1}{2}} = \left(\alpha^{\frac{3^m-1}{4}}\right)^2$. Therefore, -1 is a square element in $\mathbb{F}_{3^m}$, which implies that $-[\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta)]^2$ is a square element in $\mathbb{F}_{3^m}$. By Lemma 3, (12) has at most one solution in $\mathcal{J}$ and then the proof is completed. $\square$

Proposition 4. For a positive integer m and a fixed $\delta \in \mathbb{F}_{2^{3m}}$, the polynomial

$$f(x) = (x^{2^m} + x + \delta)^s + x$$

is a permutation of $\mathbb{F}_{2^{3m}}$ if one of the following conditions holds:

- (i) $s = 2^{2m} + 1$;
- (ii) $s = 2^{im-1} + 2^{m-1}$, $\gcd((i-1)m-1, 3m) = 1$, $i \in \{2, 3\}$.

Proof. By Lemma 2, it suffices to prove that for each $d \in \mathcal{J}$, the equation

$$(x + \delta)^{2^{ms}} + (x + \delta)^s + x = d \quad (13)$$

has at most one solution in $\mathcal{J}$.

(i) For $s = 2^{2m} + 1$, since $x^{2^{2m}} + x^{2^m} = x$ for $x \in \mathcal{J}$, (13) is equivalent to

$$\begin{aligned}
& (x + \delta)^{2^m(2^{2m}+1)} + (x + \delta)^{2^{2m}+1} + x \\
&= (x + \delta)^{2^m+1} + (x + \delta)^{2^{2m}+1} + x \\
&= (x + \delta) \left((x + \delta)^{2^{2m}} + (x + \delta)^{2^m} \right) + x \\
&= (x + \delta)(x + \delta^{2^{2m}} + \delta^{2^m}) + x \\
&= x^2 + (\delta^{2^{2m}} + \delta^{2^m} + \delta + 1)x + \delta(\delta^{2^{2m}} + \delta^{2^m}) \\
&= x^2 + (\text{Tr}_m^{3m}(\delta) + 1)x + \delta(\delta^{2^{2m}} + \delta^{2^m}) \\
&= d
\end{aligned}$$

and then

$$x^2 + (\text{Tr}_m^{3m}(\delta) + 1)x = \delta(\delta^{2^{2m}} + \delta^{2^m}) + d. \quad (14)$$

By Lemma 3, (14) has at most one solution in $\mathcal{J}$.

(ii) We only give the proof for $i = 2$ since the case that $i = 3$ can be proven similarly. Raising both sides of (13) to the power 2, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
& (x + \delta)^{2^m(2^{2m}+2^m)} + (x + \delta)^{2^{2m}+2^m} + x^2 \\
&= (x + \delta)^{2^{2m}+1} + (x + \delta)^{2^{2m}+2^m} + x^2 \\
&= (x + \delta)^{2^{2m}} \left((x + \delta)^{2^m} + x + \delta \right) + x^2 \\
&= (x + \delta)^{2^{2m}} (x^{2^{2m}} + \delta^{2^m} + \delta) + x^2 \\
&= x^{2^{2m}+1} + (\delta^{2^{2m}} + \delta^{2^m} + \delta)x^{2^{2m}} + \delta^{2^{2m}}(\delta^{2^m} + \delta) + x^2 \\
&= (x^{2^{2m}} + x)^2 + \text{Tr}_m^{3m}(\delta)x^{2^{2m}} + \delta^{2^{2m}}(\delta^{2^m} + \delta) \\
&= x^{2^{2m}+1} + \text{Tr}_m^{3m}(\delta)x^{2^{2m}} + \delta^{2^{2m}}(\delta^{2^m} + \delta) \\
&= d^2,
\end{aligned}$$

where the third and sixth equal signs hold due to $x^{2^{2m}} + x^{2^m} + x = 0$. Then we have

$$x^{2^{2m}+1} + \text{Tr}_m^{3m}(\delta)x^{2^{2m}} = \delta^{2^{2m}}(\delta^{2^m} + \delta) + d^2, \quad (15)$$

By Lemma 3, (15) has at most one solution in $\mathcal{J}$ due to $\gcd(-m+1, 3m) = \gcd(m-1, 3m) = 1$. $\square$

4 PPs $f(x)$ over $\mathbb{F}_{p^n}$ with $s_1 \equiv p^t s_2 \pmod{p^m - 1}$

In this section, we investigate the PPs having the form as in (2) and the exponents satisfy $s_1 \equiv s_2 p^t \pmod{p^m - 1}$ for an integer t .

4.1 PPs over $\mathbb{F}_{p^n}$ with $s_1 \equiv s_2 \pmod{p^m - 1}$

This subsection studies eight classes of permutation polynomials of the form (2) over $\mathbb{F}_{p^n}$ with $s_1 \equiv s_2 \pmod{p^m - 1}$.

The first class of permutation polynomials investigated here satisfies $s_1 = p^m s_2$ and $n = 2m$ or $3m$.

Proposition 5. *For positive integers m, r, s and a fixed $\delta \in \mathbb{F}_{p^{rm}}$, the polynomial*

$$f(x) = (x^{p^m} - x + \delta)^{p^m s} + (x^{p^m} - x + \delta)^s + x$$

is a permutation of $\mathbb{F}_{p^{rm}}$ if one of the following conditions holds:

- (i) $r = 2$;
- (ii) $r = 3, p = 2, s \in \{2^m + 1, 2^{(i+1)m-1} + 2^{im-1}\}, \gcd(im + 1, rm) = 1, i \in \{1, 2\}$.

Proof. For each $d \in \mathcal{J}$ defined by (3), from Lemma 2, it suffices to prove that

$$(x + \delta)^{p^{2m}s} - (x + \delta)^{p^m s} + (x + \delta)^{p^m s} - (x + \delta)^s + x = d$$

has at most one solution in $\mathcal{J}$. The above equation is equivalent to

$$(x + \delta)^{p^{2m}s} - (x + \delta)^s + x = d. \tag{16}$$

(i) For $r = 2$, (16) becomes $x = d$, i.e., $x = d$ is its unique solution.

(ii) Since proofs for different s are similar, we only prove the case $s = 2^m + 1$. Given $p = 2, r = 3$ and $x^{2^{2m}} + x^{2^m} + x = 0$ for $x \in \mathcal{J}$, (16) becomes

$$\begin{aligned} & (x + \delta)^{2^{2m}+1} + (x + \delta)^{2^m+1} + x \\ &= \left(x^{2^{2m}+1} + \delta x^{2^{2m}} + \delta^{2^{2m}} x + \delta^{2^{2m}+1} \right) + \left(x^{2^m+1} + \delta x^{2^m} + \delta^{2^m} x + \delta^{2^m+1} \right) + x \\ &= x^{2^{2m}+1} + x^{2^m+1} + \delta(x^{2^{2m}} + x^{2^m}) + (\delta^{2^{2m}} + \delta^{2^m})x + \delta^{2^{2m}+1} + \delta^{2^m+1} + x \\ &= x(x^{2^{2m}} + x^{2^m}) + \delta x + (\delta^{2^{2m}} + \delta^{2^m} + 1)x + \delta^{2^{2m}+1} + \delta^{2^m+1} \\ &= x^2 + (\text{Tr}_m^{3m}(\delta) + 1)x + \delta^{2^{2m}+1} + \delta^{2^m+1} \\ &= d, \end{aligned}$$

i.e.,

$$x^2 + (\text{Tr}_m^{3m}(\delta) + 1)x = \delta(\delta^{2^{2m}} + \delta^{2^m}) + d. \tag{17}$$

By Lemma 3, (17) has at most one solution in $\mathcal{J}$. This finishes the proof. $\square$

Proposition 6. For two nonnegative integers i, m with $m > 0$, and a fixed $\delta \in \mathbb{F}_{p^{2m}}$, the polynomial

$$f(x) = (x^{p^m} - x + \delta)^{\frac{i(p^{2m}-1)}{p^2-1}+1} + (x^{p^m} - x + \delta)^{\frac{i(p^{2m}-1)}{p^2-1}+p^m} + x$$

is a permutation of $\mathbb{F}_{p^{2m}}$ if one of the following conditions holds:

- (i) $p = 2$;
- (ii) p is an odd prime, and m is even.

Proof. If $i = 0$, then $f(x) = x + \delta^{p^m} + \delta$, which is a permutation under Condition (i) or (ii). In the sequel, we only consider the case $i \neq 0$.

By Lemma 2, it suffices to prove that for each $d \in \mathcal{J}$, the equation

$$\begin{aligned} & (x + \delta)^{p^m \left(\frac{i(p^{2m}-1)}{p^2-1} + 1 \right)} - (x + \delta)^{\frac{i(p^{2m}-1)}{p^2-1}+1} + (x + \delta)^{p^m \left(\frac{i(p^{2m}-1)}{p^2-1} + p^m \right)} \\ & - (x + \delta)^{\frac{i(p^{2m}-1)}{p^2-1}+p^m} + x \\ = & (x + \delta)^{\frac{p^m i(p^{2m}-1)}{p^2-1}} \left((x + \delta)^{p^m} + x + \delta \right) - (x + \delta)^{\frac{i(p^{2m}-1)}{p^2-1}} \\ & \left((x + \delta)^{p^m} + x + \delta \right) + x \\ = & (x^{p^m} + \delta^{p^m} + x + \delta) \left((x + \delta)^{\frac{p^m i(p^{2m}-1)}{p^2-1}} - (x + \delta)^{\frac{i(p^{2m}-1)}{p^2-1}} \right) + x \\ = & \text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta) \left((x + \delta)^{\frac{p^m i(p^{2m}-1)}{p^2-1}} - (x + \delta)^{\frac{i(p^{2m}-1)}{p^2-1}} \right) + x \\ = & d \end{aligned}$$

has a unique solution in $\mathcal{J}$, where the third equal sign holds due to $x^{p^m} + x = 0$ for $x \in \mathcal{J}$. The above equation can be written as

$$\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta) \left((x + \delta)^{\frac{p^m i(p^{2m}-1)}{p^2-1}} - (x + \delta)^{\frac{i(p^{2m}-1)}{p^2-1}} \right) + x = d. \quad (18)$$

(i) For $p = 2$, (18) becomes

$$\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta) \left((x + \delta)^{\frac{2^m i(2^{2m}-1)}{3}} + (x + \delta)^{\frac{i(2^{2m}-1)}{3}} \right) + x = d. \quad (19)$$

If m is even, $\frac{2^m i(2^{2m}-1)}{3} \equiv \frac{i(2^{2m}-1)}{3} \pmod{2^{2m}-1}$ and then

$$(x + \delta)^{\frac{2^m i(2^{2m}-1)}{3}} + (x + \delta)^{\frac{i(2^{2m}-1)}{3}} = 0.$$

This implies $x = d$, which is the unique solution of (19) in $\mathcal{J}$.

If m is odd, we have $\frac{2^m i(2^{2m}-1)}{3} \equiv \frac{2i(2^{2m}-1)}{3} \pmod{2^{2m}-1}$ and then (19) can be written as

$$\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta) \left((x + \delta)^{\frac{2i(2^{2m}-1)}{3}} + (x + \delta)^{\frac{i(2^{2m}-1)}{3}} \right) + x = d. \quad (20)$$

When $\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta) = 0$, $x = d$ is the unique solution of (19). When $\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta) \neq 0$, (20) becomes

$$(x + \delta)^{\frac{2i(2^{2m}-1)}{3}} + (x + \delta)^{\frac{i(2^{2m}-1)}{3}} = \frac{x + d}{\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta)}.$$

Thus, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{x+d}{\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta)} &= (x + \delta)^{\frac{2i(2^{2m}-1)}{3}} + (x + \delta)^{\frac{i(2^{2m}-1)}{3}} \\ &= (x + \delta)^{\frac{2i(2^{2m}-1)}{3}} + (x + \delta)^{i(2^{2m}-1) + \frac{i(2^{2m}-1)}{3}} \\ &= (x + \delta)^{\frac{2i(2^{2m}-1)}{3}} + (x + \delta)^{\frac{4i(2^{2m}-1)}{3}} \\ &= \left((x + \delta)^{\frac{2i(2^{2m}-1)}{3}} + (x + \delta)^{\frac{i(2^{2m}-1)}{3}} \right)^2 \\ &= \left(\frac{x+d}{\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta)} \right)^2, \end{aligned}$$

i.e., $\frac{(x+d)^2}{[\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta)]^2} = \frac{x+d}{\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta)}$. This implies $x = \text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta) + d$ or $x = d$. We claim that $x = \text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta) + d$ and $x = d$ can not hold simultaneously. Otherwise, from (20) we have

$$\begin{cases} (\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta) + d + \delta)^{\frac{2i(2^{2m}-1)}{3}} + (\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta) + d + \delta)^{\frac{i(2^{2m}-1)}{3}} = 1, \\ (d + \delta)^{\frac{2i(2^{2m}-1)}{3}} + (d + \delta)^{\frac{i(2^{2m}-1)}{3}} = 0. \end{cases}$$

Since $d^{2^m} = d$ for $d \in \mathcal{J}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} 1 &= (\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta) + d + \delta)^{\frac{2i(2^{2m}-1)}{3}} + (\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta) + d + \delta)^{\frac{i(2^{2m}-1)}{3}} \\ &= (d + \delta^{2^m})^{\frac{2i(2^{2m}-1)}{3}} + (d + \delta^{2^m})^{\frac{i(2^{2m}-1)}{3}} \\ &= (d^{2^m} + \delta^{2^m})^{\frac{2i(2^{2m}-1)}{3}} + (d^{2^m} + \delta^{2^m})^{\frac{i(2^{2m}-1)}{3}} \\ &= \left((d + \delta)^{\frac{2i(2^{2m}-1)}{3}} + (d + \delta)^{\frac{i(2^{2m}-1)}{3}} \right)^{2^m} \\ &= 0. \end{aligned}$$

This is impossible and then (20) has at most one solution in $\mathcal{J}$.

(ii) For an odd prime p , since m is even, $\frac{p^m i(p^{2m}-1)}{p^2-1} \equiv \frac{i(p^{2m}-1)}{p^2-1} \pmod{p^{2m}-1}$. Then

$$(x + \delta)^{\frac{p^m i(p^{2m}-1)}{p^2-1}} - (x + \delta)^{\frac{i(p^{2m}-1)}{p^2-1}} = 0$$

and (18) becomes $x = d$, i.e., $x = d$ is the unique solution of (18) in $\mathcal{J}$. $\square$

The following example illustrates that $f(x)$ in Proposition 6 cannot permute $\mathbb{F}_{p^{2m}}$ for all odd prime p if m is odd, and the assumption in Proposition 6 is necessary.

Example 2. Take $p = 3$, $m = 3$, $i = 1$ and $\delta = \omega$, where ω is a root of the primitive polynomial $x^6 + 2x^4 + x^2 + 2x + 2$ over $\mathbb{F}_3$. By computer, it can be verified that

$$f(x) = (x^{27} - x + \omega)^{92} + (x^{27} - x + \omega)^{108} + x$$

is not a permutation of $\mathbb{F}_{3^6}$.

Proposition 7. For three nonnegative integers i, j, m with $m > 0$, and a fixed $\delta \in \mathbb{F}_{p^{2m}}$, the polynomial

$$f(x) = (x^{p^m} - x + \delta)^{(p-1)p^{m+i}+p^j} + (x^{p^m} - x + \delta)^{(p-1)p^{m+i}+p^{m+j}} + x$$

is a permutation of $\mathbb{F}_{p^{2m}}$ if one of the following conditions holds:

- (i) $p = 2$;
- (ii) $p = 3$ and $\gcd(i, 2m) = 1$.

Proof. Since $x^{p^m} + x = 0$ for $x \in \mathcal{J}$, by Lemma 2, it suffices to prove that for each $x \in \mathcal{J}$, the equation

$$\begin{aligned} & (x + \delta)^{(p-1)p^i+p^{m+j}} - (x + \delta)^{(p-1)p^{m+i}+p^j} + (x + \delta)^{(p-1)p^i+p^j} \\ & - (x + \delta)^{(p-1)p^{m+i}+p^{m+j}} + x \\ = & (x + \delta)^{(p-1)p^i} \left((x + \delta)^{p^{m+j}} + (x + \delta)^{p^j} \right) - \\ & (x + \delta)^{(p-1)p^{m+i}} \left((x + \delta)^{p^{m+j}} + (x + \delta)^{p^j} \right) + x \\ = & \left((x + \delta)^{p^m} + (x + \delta) \right)^{p^j} \left((x + \delta)^{p-1} - (x + \delta)^{(p-1)p^m} \right)^{p^i} + x \\ = & (\delta^{p^m} + \delta)^{p^j} \left((x + \delta)^{p-1} - (x + \delta)^{(p-1)p^m} \right)^{p^i} + x \\ = & d, \end{aligned}$$

i.e.,

$$[\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta)]^{p^j} \left[(x + \delta)^{p-1} - (x + \delta)^{(p-1)p^m} \right]^{p^i} + x = d \quad (21)$$

has at most one solution in $\mathcal{J}$.

- (i) For $p = 2$, (21) is equivalent to

$$[\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta)]^{2^j} \left[(x + \delta) + (x + \delta)^{2^m} \right]^{2^i} + x = d,$$

which can be reduced to

$$x + [\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta)]^{2^i+2^j} = d$$

due to $x^{2^m} + x = 0$ for $x \in \mathcal{J}$. Therefore, $x = [\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta)]^{2^i+2^j} + d$ is the unique solution of (21).

(ii) For $p = 3$, note that $x^{3^m} = -x$ for $x \in \mathcal{J}$, then (21) is equivalent to

$$\begin{aligned}
& [\mathrm{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta)]^{3^j} [(x + \delta)^2 - (x + \delta)^{2 \cdot 3^m}]^{3^i} + x \\
&= [\mathrm{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta)]^{3^j} [(x + \delta)^2 - (x - \delta^{3^m})^2]^{3^i} + x \\
&= [\mathrm{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta)]^{3^j} [(x^2 - \delta x + \delta^2 - (x^2 + \delta^{3^m} x + \delta^{2 \cdot 3^m})]^{3^i} + x \\
&= [\mathrm{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta)]^{3^j} [-(\delta^{3^m} + \delta)x + \delta^2 - \delta^{2 \cdot 3^m}]^{3^i} + x \\
&= x - [\mathrm{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta)]^{3^i+3^j} x^{3^i} - [\mathrm{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta)]^{3^j} (\delta^{3^m} + \delta)^{3^i} (\delta^{3^m} - \delta)^{3^i} \\
&= x - [\mathrm{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta)]^{3^i+3^j} x^{3^i} - [\mathrm{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta)]^{3^i+3^j} (\delta^{3^m} - \delta)^{3^i} \\
&= d,
\end{aligned}$$

i.e.,

$$x - [\mathrm{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta)]^{3^i+3^j} x^{3^i} = [\mathrm{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta)]^{3^i+3^j} (\delta^{3^m} - \delta)^{3^i} + d. \quad (22)$$

Raising both sides of (22) to the power 3^{2m-i} , we have

$$x^{3^{2m-i}} - [\mathrm{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta)]^{3^{2m-i}(3^i+3^j)} x = \left([\mathrm{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta)]^{3^i+3^j} (\delta^{3^m} - \delta)^{3^i} + d \right)^{3^{2m-i}}. \quad (23)$$

Since $\gcd(2m - i, 2m) = \gcd(i, 2m) = 1$ and $[\mathrm{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta)]^{3^{2m-i}(3^i+3^j)}$ is a square element of $\mathbb{F}_{3^m}$, (23) has at most one solution in $\mathcal{J}$ by Lemma 3. $\square$

The example shows that the result in Proposition 7 does not necessarily hold if the requirement on p is removed.

Example 3. Take $p = 5$, $m = 2$, $i = 1$, $j = 0$ and $\delta = \omega^{14}$, where ω is a root of the primitive polynomial $x^4 + 4x^2 + 4x + 2$ over $\mathbb{F}_5$. By computer, it can be verified that

$$f(x) = (x^{25} - x + \omega^{14})^{501} + (x^{25} - x + \omega^{14})^{525} + x$$

is not a permutation of $\mathbb{F}_{5^4}$.

In the above three classes of permutation polynomials over $\mathbb{F}_{p^n}$, there is no restriction on δ . In the following, we propose a class of permutation polynomials over $\mathbb{F}_{p^n}$ with $\mathrm{Tr}_m^n(\delta) = 0$.

Proposition 8. For a positive integer m and a fixed $\delta \in \mathbb{F}_{p^{3m}}$ with $\mathrm{Tr}_m^{3m}(\delta) = 0$, the polynomial

$$f(x) = (x^{p^m} - x + \delta)^{2p^{2m}+p^m} + (x^{p^m} - x + \delta)^{p^{2m}+2p^m} + x$$

is a permutation of $\mathbb{F}_{p^{3m}}$.

Proof. By Lemma 2, it suffices to prove that for any $d \in \mathcal{J}$, the equation

$$(x + \delta)^{p^{2m}+2} - (x + \delta)^{2p^{2m}+p^m} + (x + \delta)^{2p^{2m}+1} - (x + \delta)^{p^{2m}+2p^m} + x = d \quad (24)$$

has at most one solution in $\mathcal{J}$. Since $\text{Tr}_m^{3m}(\delta) = 0$ and $\text{Tr}_m^{3m}(x + \delta) = 0$, we have

$$(x + \delta)^{p^m} + x + \delta = -(x + \delta)^{p^{2m}}.$$

Thus, the left side of (24) becomes

$$\begin{aligned} & (x + \delta)^{p^{2m+2}} - (x + \delta)^{2p^{2m}+p^m} + (x + \delta)^{2p^{2m}+1} - (x + \delta)^{p^{2m}+2p^m} + x \\ = & (x + \delta)^{2p^{2m}} (x + \delta - (x + \delta)^{p^m}) + (x + \delta)^{p^{2m}} ((x + \delta)^2 - (x + \delta)^{2p^m}) + x \\ = & (x + \delta)^{2p^{2m}} (x + \delta - (x + \delta)^{p^m}) + (x + \delta)^{p^{2m}} ((x + \delta) - (x + \delta)^{p^m}) ((x + \delta) + (x + \delta)^{p^m}) \\ & + x \\ = & (x + \delta)^{2p^{2m}} (x + \delta - (x + \delta)^{p^m}) - (x + \delta)^{2p^{2m}} ((x + \delta) - (x + \delta)^{p^m}) + x \\ = & x. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $x = d$ is the unique solution of (24) in $\mathcal{J}$. $\square$

In the following, we propose a class of permutation polynomials having the form as in (2) over $\mathbb{F}_{2^n}$ with $n = 3m$.

Proposition 9. *For positive integers m, i with $\gcd(jm + i, 3m) = 1$, $j \in \{0, 1, 2\}$, and a fixed $\delta \in \mathbb{F}_{2^{3m}}$, the polynomial*

$$f(x) = (x^{2^m} + x + \delta)^{2^{jm+i}+2^{2m}} + (x^{2^m} + x + \delta)^{2^{(j+2)m+i+1}} + x$$

is a permutation of $\mathbb{F}_{2^{3m}}$.

Proof. Since proofs for different j are similar, we only prove the case $j = 0$. By Lemma 2, it suffices to prove that for any $d \in \mathcal{J}$, the equation

$$\begin{aligned} & (x + \delta)^{2^m(2^{2m}+2^i)} + (x + \delta)^{2^{2m}+2^i} + (x + \delta)^{2^m(2^{2m+i}+1)} + (x + \delta)^{2^{2m+i}+1} + x \\ = & (x + \delta)^{2^{m+i}+1} + (x + \delta)^{2^{2m}+2^i} + (x + \delta)^{2^m+2^i} + (x + \delta)^{2^{2m+i}+1} + x \\ = & (x + \delta)^{2^i} \left((x + \delta)^{2^{2m}} + (x + \delta)^{2^m} \right) + (x + \delta) \left((x + \delta)^{2^{m+i}} + (x + \delta)^{2^{2m+i}} \right) + x \\ = & (x + \delta)^{2^i} (x + \delta^{2^{2m}} + \delta^{2^m}) + (x + \delta)(x + \delta^{2^{2m}} + \delta^{2^m})^{2^i} + x \\ = & \left(x^{2^i+1} + (\delta^{2^{2m}} + \delta^{2^m})x^{2^i} + \delta^{2^i}x + \delta^{2^i}(\delta^{2^{2m}} + \delta^{2^m}) \right) \\ & + \left(x^{2^i+1} + \delta x^{2^i} + (\delta^{2^{2m}} + \delta^{2^m})^{2^i}x + \delta(\delta^{2^{2m}} + \delta^{2^m})^{2^i} \right) + x \\ = & \text{Tr}_m^{3m}(\delta)x^{2^i} + \left([\text{Tr}_m^{3m}(\delta)]^{2^i} + 1 \right) x + \delta^{2^{2m+i}+1} + \delta^{2^{m+i}+1} + \delta^{2^{2m}+2^i} + \delta^{2^m+2^i} \\ = & d \end{aligned}$$

has at most one solution in $\mathcal{J}$, where the third equal sign holds due to (4). Thus, we have

$$\text{Tr}_m^{3m}(\delta)x^{2^i} + \left([\text{Tr}_m^{3m}(\delta)]^{2^i} + 1 \right) x = \delta^{2^{2m+i}+1} + \delta^{2^{m+i}+1} + \delta^{2^{2m}+2^i} + \delta^{2^m+2^i} + d. \quad (25)$$

If $\text{Tr}_m^{3m}(\delta) = 0$, then

$$x = \delta^{2^{2m+i+1}} + \delta^{2^{m+i+1}} + \delta^{2^{2m+2^i}} + \delta^{2^m+2^i} + d$$

is the unique solution in $\mathcal{J}$ of (25). If $\text{Tr}_m^{3m}(\delta) \neq 0$, (25) becomes

$$x^{2^i} + \frac{[\text{Tr}_m^{3m}(\delta)]^{2^i} + 1}{\text{Tr}_m^{3m}(\delta)} x = \frac{\delta^{2^{2m+i+1}} + \delta^{2^{m+i+1}} + \delta^{2^{2m+2^i}} + \delta^{2^m+2^i} + d}{\text{Tr}_m^{3m}(\delta)}. \quad (26)$$

By Lemma 3, (26) has at most one solution in $\mathcal{J}$ due to $\text{gcd}(i, 3m) = 1$. $\square$

In the sequel, three classes of permutation polynomials over $\mathbb{F}_{p^n}$ are proposed, where p is an odd prime. For $n = 2m$, we investigate a class of permutation polynomials such that $(1 - [\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta)]^4)$ is a square element of $\mathbb{F}_{p^m}$. For $n = 3m$, two classes of permutation polynomials with fractional s_1, s_2 are considered.

Proposition 10. *For a positive integer m and a fixed $\delta \in \mathbb{F}_{3^{2m}}$, if $(1 - [\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta)]^4)$ is a square element in $\mathbb{F}_{3^m}$, then the polynomial*

$$f(x) = (x^{3^m} - x + \delta)^{3^m+4} + (x^{3^m} - x + \delta)^5 + x$$

is a permutation of $\mathbb{F}_{3^{2m}}$.

Proof. Note that $x^{3^m} + x = 0$ for $x \in \mathcal{J}$. By Lemma 2, it suffices to prove that for each given $d \in \mathcal{J}$, the equation

$$\begin{aligned} & (x + \delta)^{3^m(3^m+4)} - (x + \delta)^{3^m+4} + (x + \delta)^{5 \cdot 3^m} - (x + \delta)^5 + x \\ = & (x + \delta)^{4 \cdot 3^m} (x + \delta) - (x + \delta)^{3^m} (x + \delta)^4 + (x + \delta)^{5 \cdot 3^m} - (x + \delta)^5 + x \\ = & (-x + \delta^{3^m})^4 (x + \delta) - (-x + \delta^{3^m}) (x + \delta)^4 + (-x + \delta^{3^m})^5 - (x + \delta)^5 + x \\ = & \left(x^5 + (\delta - \delta^{3^m})x^4 - \delta^{3^m+1}x^3 - \delta^{3^m+1}x^2 + (\delta^{4 \cdot 3^m} - \delta^{3^m+1+1})x + \delta^{4 \cdot 3^m+1} \right) \\ & - (-x^5 + (\delta^{3^m} - \delta)x^4 + \delta^{3^m+1}x^3 - \delta^3x^2 - (\delta^4 - \delta^{3^m+3})x + \delta^{3^m+4}) \\ & + (-x^5 - \delta^{3^m}x^4 - \delta^{2 \cdot 3^m}x^3 + \delta^{3^m+1}x^2 + \delta^{4 \cdot 3^m}x + \delta^{5 \cdot 3^m}) \\ & - (x^5 - \delta x^4 + \delta^2x^3 + \delta^3x^2 - \delta^4x + \delta^5) + x \\ = & -(\delta^{3^m+1} + \delta^{2 \cdot 3^m} + \delta^2)x^3 + (1 - \delta^{4 \cdot 3^m} - \delta^{3^m+1+1} - \delta^{3^m+3} - \delta^4)x \\ & + \delta^{4 \cdot 3^m+1} - \delta^{3^m+4} + \delta^{5 \cdot 3^m} - \delta^5 \\ = & -[\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta)]^2 x^3 + (1 - [\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta)]^4)x + \text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta)(\delta^{4 \cdot 3^m} - \delta^4) \\ = & d \end{aligned}$$

has at most one solution in $\mathcal{J}$. Then we have

$$-[\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta)]^2 x^3 + (1 - [\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta)]^4)x = -\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta)(\delta^{4 \cdot 3^m} - \delta^4) + d. \quad (27)$$

When $\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta) = 0$, $x = d$ is its unique solution. When $\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta) \neq 0$, (27) becomes

$$x^3 + \frac{[\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta)]^4 - 1}{[\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta)]^2}x = \frac{\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta)(\delta^{4 \cdot 3^m} - \delta^4) - d}{[\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta)]^2}. \quad (28)$$

Since $1 - [\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta)]^4$ is a square element of $\mathbb{F}_{3^m}$, $\frac{[\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta)]^4 - 1}{[\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta)]^2}$ is also a square element of $\mathbb{F}_{3^m}$. Then by Lemma 3, (27) has at most one solution in $\mathcal{J}$ and the proof is completed. $\square$

Example 4. Take $m = 3$ and $p = 3$. By computer, there are 405 different $\delta \in \mathbb{F}_{3^6}$ such that $(1 - [\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta)]^4)$ is a square element, and these δ are exactly all the elements in $\mathbb{F}_{3^6}$ such that

$$f(x) = (x^{27} - x + \delta)^{31} + (x^{27} - x + \delta)^5 + x$$

is a permutation of $\mathbb{F}_{3^6}$. Moreover, it is verified that the polynomial $f(x)$ is not a permutation if $(1 - [\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta)]^4)$ is not a square element of $\mathbb{F}_{3^6}$. All possible elements $\delta \in \mathbb{F}_{3^6}$ such that $f(x)$ is a permutation over $\mathbb{F}_{3^6}$ are given by Proposition 10. Hence the condition on δ in Proposition 10 is reasonable.

Proposition 11. For three nonnegative integers m, i, j with $m > 0$ and a fixed $\delta \in \mathbb{F}_{3^{3m}}$, the polynomial

$$f(x) = (x^{3^m} - x + \delta)^{\frac{3^{3m}-1}{2}+3^{im}} + (x^{3^m} - x + \delta)^{\frac{3^{3m}-1}{2}+3^{jm}} + x$$

is a permutation of $\mathbb{F}_{3^{3m}}$ if one of the following conditions holds:

- (i) $i = 0, j = 2$;
- (ii) $i = 0, j = 1, \text{Tr}_m^{3m}(\delta) = 0$;
- (iii) $i = 1, j = 2, \text{Tr}_m^{3m}(\delta) = 0$.

Proof. We only give the proof for Case (i) since the other two cases can be proved similarly. By Lemma 2, it suffices to prove that for each $d \in \mathcal{J}$, the equation

$$(x + \delta)^{3^m \left(\frac{3^{3m}-1}{2} + 1 \right)} - (x + \delta)^{\frac{3^{3m}-1}{2} + 1} + (x + \delta)^{3^m \left(\frac{3^{3m}-1}{2} + 3^{2m} \right)} - (x + \delta)^{\frac{3^{3m}-1}{2} + 3^{2m}} + x = d \quad (29)$$

has at most one solution in $\mathcal{J}$.

If $x + \delta = 0$, then $x = -\delta = d$.

In the sequel, we only consider the case $x + \delta \neq 0$.

Note that $x^{3^{2m}} + x^{3^m} + x = 0$ for $x \in \mathcal{J}$, and $(x + \delta)^{\frac{3^{3m}-1}{2}} = 1$ or -1 . If $(x + \delta)^{\frac{3^{3m}-1}{2}} = 1$, (29) becomes

$$x^{3^{2m}} = \delta^{3^{2m}} - \delta^{3^m} + d. \quad (30)$$

Raising both sides of (30) to the power 3^m , we have

$$x = -\delta^{3^{2m}} + \delta + d^{3^m},$$

which implies

$$(-\delta^{3^{2m}} - \delta + d^{3^m})^{\frac{3^{3m}-1}{2}} = 1. \quad (31)$$

If $(x + \delta)^{\frac{3^{3m}-1}{2}} = -1$, in the same way we have

$$x = -\delta^{3^m} + \delta + d^{3^{2m}}$$

and then

$$(-\delta^{3^m} - \delta + d^{3^{2m}})^{\frac{3^{3m}-1}{2}} = -1. \quad (32)$$

When $d = -\delta$, we have $\delta \in \mathcal{J}$ and then $\delta^{3^{2m}} + \delta^{3^m} + \delta = 0$. Consequently, $-\delta^{3^{2m}} + \delta + d^{3^m} = -\delta^{3^m} + \delta + d^{3^{2m}} = -\delta$. Thus, in this case, Equation (29) has the solution $x = -\delta$ whenever $(x + \delta)^{\frac{3^{3m}-1}{2}} = 1$ or -1 .

When $d \neq -\delta$, we claim that $x = -\delta^{3^{2m}} + \delta + d^{3^m}$ and $x = -\delta^{3^m} + \delta + d^{3^{2m}}$ can not hold simultaneously. Otherwise, by (31) and (32)

$$-1 = (-\delta^{3^m} - \delta + d^{3^{2m}})^{\frac{3^{3m}-1}{2}} = \left((-\delta^{3^{2m}} - \delta + d^{3^m})^{\frac{3^{3m}-1}{2}} \right)^{3^m} = 1^{3^m} = 1.$$

This is impossible. Consequently, (29) has at most one solution in $\mathcal{J}$. $\square$

Example 5. Take $m = 1$ and $p = 3$. By computer, it can be verified that

$$f_1(x) = (x^3 - x + \delta)^{14} + (x^3 - x + \delta)^{22} + x$$

permutes $\mathbb{F}_{3^3}$ for all $\delta \in \mathbb{F}_{3^3}$. There are 9 different $\delta \in \mathbb{F}_{3^3}$ satisfying that $\text{Tr}_1^3(\delta) = 0$, and these δ are exactly all the elements in $\mathbb{F}_{3^3}$ such that

$$f_2(x) = (x^3 - x + \delta)^{14} + (x^3 - x + \delta)^{16} + x$$

and

$$f_3(x) = (x^3 - x + \delta)^{16} + (x^3 - x + \delta)^{22} + x$$

are permutations of $\mathbb{F}_{3^3}$. Moreover, it is verified that neither $f_2(x)$ nor $f_3(x)$ is a permutation of $\mathbb{F}_{3^3}$ if $\text{Tr}_1^3(\delta) \neq 0$.

Proposition 12. For a positive integer m , an odd prime p , and a fixed $\delta \in \mathbb{F}_{p^{3m}}$ with $\text{Tr}_m^{3m}(\delta) = 0$, the polynomial

$$f(x) = (x^{p^m} - x + \delta)^{\frac{p^{3m}-1}{2} + p^{2m} + p^m - 1} + (x^{p^m} - x + \delta)^{\frac{p^{3m}-1}{2} + 2p^m - 1} + x$$

is a permutation of $\mathbb{F}_{p^{3m}}$.

Proof. By Lemma 2, it suffices to prove that for any $d \in \mathcal{J}$, the equation

$$\begin{aligned} & (x + \delta)^{p^m \left(\frac{p^{3m-1}}{2} + p^{2m} + p^{m-1} \right)} - (x + \delta)^{\frac{p^{3m-1}}{2} + p^{2m} + p^{m-1}} + (x + \delta)^{p^m \left(\frac{p^{3m-1}}{2} + 2p^{m-1} \right)} \\ & - (x + \delta)^{\frac{p^{3m-1}}{2} + 2p^{m-1}} + x = d \end{aligned} \quad (33)$$

has at most one solution in $\mathcal{J}$.

If $x + \delta = 0$, then $x = -\delta = d$.

In the case $x + \delta \neq 0$, when $(x + \delta)^{\frac{p^{3m-1}}{2}} = 1$, (33) becomes

$$\begin{aligned} & (x + \delta)^{p^{2m} - p^m + 1} - (x + \delta)^{p^{2m} + p^m - 1} + (x + \delta)^{2p^{2m} - p^m} - (x + \delta)^{2p^{m-1}} + x \\ & = \left((x + \delta)^{p^{2m} - p^m + 1} + (x + \delta)^{2p^{2m} - p^m} \right) - \left((x + \delta)^{p^{2m} + p^m - 1} + (x + \delta)^{2p^{m-1}} \right) + x \\ & = (x + \delta)^{p^{2m} - p^m} \left((x + \delta)^{p^{2m}} + x + \delta \right) - (x + \delta)^{p^{m-1}} \left((x + \delta)^{p^{2m}} + (x + \delta)^{p^m} \right) + x \\ & = -(x + \delta)^{p^{2m}} + (x + \delta)^{p^m} + x \\ & = (-x^{p^{2m}} + x^{p^m} + x) - \delta^{p^{2m}} + \delta^{p^m} \\ & = -2x^{p^{2m}} - \delta^{p^{2m}} + \delta^{p^m} \\ & = d \end{aligned} \quad (34)$$

since $\text{Tr}_m^{3m}(\delta) = 0$ and $\text{Tr}_m^{3m}(x) = 0$. The last two lines of (34) imply that

$$x^{p^{2m}} = \frac{1}{2}(-\delta^{p^{2m}} + \delta^{p^m} - d)$$

and then

$$x = \frac{1}{2}(-\delta^{p^{2m}} + \delta^{p^m} - d)^{p^m}.$$

When $(x + \delta)^{\frac{p^{3m-1}}{2}} = -1$, we can have

$$x = \frac{1}{2}(\delta^{p^{2m}} - \delta^{p^m} - d)^{p^{2m}}$$

in a similar way. Denote $\alpha = \frac{1}{2}(-\delta^{p^{2m}} + \delta^{p^m} - d)^{p^m}$ and $\beta = \frac{1}{2}(\delta^{p^{2m}} - \delta^{p^m} - d)^{p^{2m}}$.

For the case $d = -\delta$, $x = -\delta = \alpha = \beta$ is the unique solution of (33). For the case $d \neq -\delta$, $x = \alpha$ and $x = \beta$ can not hold simultaneously. Otherwise, by $\text{Tr}_m^{3m}(\delta) = 0$,

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= (\alpha + \delta)^{\frac{p^{3m-1}}{2}} + (\beta + \delta)^{\frac{p^{3m-1}}{2}} \\ &= \left(\frac{1}{2}(-\delta^{p^{2m}} + \delta^{p^m} - d)^{p^m} + \delta \right)^{\frac{p^{3m-1}}{2}} + \left(\frac{1}{2}(\delta^{p^{2m}} - \delta^{p^m} - d)^{p^{2m}} + \delta \right)^{\frac{p^{3m-1}}{2}} \\ &= \left(-\frac{1}{2}(\delta + d)^{p^m} \right)^{\frac{p^{3m-1}}{2}} + \left(-\frac{1}{2}(\delta + d)^{p^{2m}} \right)^{\frac{p^{3m-1}}{2}} \\ &= \pm 2. \end{aligned}$$

This is impossible. Consequently, (33) has at most one solution in $\mathcal{J}$. □

Example 6. Take $m = 2$ and $p = 3$. By computer, it can be verified that there are 81 different $\delta \in \mathbb{F}_{3^6}$ satisfying that $\text{Tr}_2^6(\delta) = 0$, and these δ are exactly all the elements in $\mathbb{F}_{3^6}$ such that

$$f(x) = (x^9 - x + \delta)^{453} + (x^9 - x + \delta)^{381} + x$$

is a permutation of $\mathbb{F}_{3^6}$. Furthermore, it can also be verified that $f(x)$ cannot permute $\mathbb{F}_{3^6}$ if $\text{Tr}_2^6(\delta) \neq 0$.

4.2 PPs $f(x)$ over $\mathbb{F}_{2^n}$ with $s_1 \equiv 2^t s_2 \pmod{2^m - 1}$ for $t > 0$

In this subsection, we propose two classes of permutation polynomials whose exponents s_1 and s_2 satisfy $s_1 \equiv 2^t s_2 \pmod{2^m - 1}$ for a positive integer t .

Proposition 13. For an even positive integer m and nonnegative integers i, j, k with $2^i \mid jm$, let δ be an element in $\mathbb{F}_{2^{2m}}$. Then

$$f(x) = (x^{2^m} + x + \delta)^{2^{\frac{jm}{2^i} + 2\frac{jm}{2^i} + \frac{km}{2}}} + (x^{2^m} + x + \delta)^{2^{\left(\frac{j}{2^i} + \frac{1}{2}\right)m} + 2^{\frac{jm}{2^i} + \frac{(k+1)m}{2}}} + x$$

is a permutation of $\mathbb{F}_{2^{2m}}$.

Proof. Denote $s_1 = 2^{\frac{jm}{2^i} + 2\frac{jm}{2^i} + \frac{km}{2}}$ and then $s_2 = 2^{\left(\frac{j}{2^i} + \frac{1}{2}\right)m} + 2^{\frac{jm}{2^i} + \frac{(k+1)m}{2}} = 2^{\frac{m}{2}} s_1$. By Lemma 2, it suffices to prove that for each $d \in \mathcal{J}$, the equation

$$(x + \delta)^{2^m s_1} + (x + \delta)^{s_1} + (x + \delta)^{2^m s_2} + (x + \delta)^{s_2} = x + d \quad (35)$$

has at most one solution in $\mathcal{J}$. Raising both sides of (35) to the power $2^{\frac{m}{2}}$, we have

$$(x + \delta)^{2^m s_1} + (x + \delta)^{s_1} + (x + \delta)^{2^m s_2} + (x + \delta)^{s_2} = x^{2^{\frac{m}{2}}} + d^{2^{\frac{m}{2}}}. \quad (36)$$

It follows from (35) and (36) that

$$(x + d)^{2^{\frac{m}{2}}} + x + d = 0. \quad (37)$$

Denote $\alpha = x + d$, then $\alpha \in \mathbb{F}_{2^{\frac{m}{2}}}$ from (37). Substituting x with $\alpha + d$ on the left side of (35) gives

$$\begin{aligned} & (x + \delta)^{2^m s_1} + (x + \delta)^{s_1} + (x + \delta)^{2^m s_2} + (x + \delta)^{s_2} \\ = & (\alpha + d + \delta)^{2^{\frac{jm}{2^i} + m} \left(1 + 2^{\frac{km}{2}}\right)} + (\alpha + d + \delta)^{2^{\frac{jm}{2^i}} \left(1 + 2^{\frac{km}{2}}\right)} + (\alpha + d + \delta)^{2^{\frac{jm}{2^i} + \frac{3m}{2}} \left(1 + 2^{\frac{km}{2}}\right)} \\ & + (\alpha + d + \delta)^{2^{\frac{jm}{2^i} + \frac{m}{2}} \left(1 + 2^{\frac{km}{2}}\right)} \\ = & \left(\text{Tr}_{m/2}^{2m}(d + \delta) + \text{Tr}_{m/2}^{2m}(d + \delta)^{2^{\frac{km}{2}}} \right)^{2^{\frac{jm}{2^i}}} \alpha^{2^{\frac{jm}{2^i}}} + \text{Tr}_{m/2}^{2m} \left((d + \delta)^{2^{\frac{jm}{2^i} + 2\frac{jm}{2^i} + \frac{km}{2}}} \right) \\ = & \text{Tr}_{m/2}^{2m} \left((d + \delta)^{2^{\frac{jm}{2^i} + 2\frac{jm}{2^i} + \frac{km}{2}}} \right). \end{aligned}$$

By (35), $x = \text{Tr}_{m/2}^{2m} \left((d + \delta)^{2^{\frac{jm}{2^i}} + 2^{\frac{jm}{2^i} + \frac{km}{2}}} \right) + d$ is the unique solution of (35) in $\mathcal{J}$. $\square$

Proposition 14. *For positive integers i, k, m with $3 \mid m, i \in \{1, 2\}$, and each element $\delta \in \mathbb{F}_{2^{2m}}$, the polynomial*

$$f(x) = (x^{2^m} + x + \delta)^{2^{\frac{im}{3}} + 2^{\frac{km}{3}}} + (x^{2^m} + x + \delta)^{2^{\frac{2im}{3}} + 2^{\frac{(k+i)m}{3}}} + x$$

is a permutation of $\mathbb{F}_{2^{2m}}$ if one of the following conditions holds:

- (i) $k \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ and $\frac{m}{3}$ is odd;
- (ii) $k \equiv i \pmod{3}$;
- (iii) $k \equiv 3 - i \pmod{3}$ and $\frac{m}{3}$ is odd.

Proof. We only prove the case that $i = 1$ since the other case can be shown similarly. Denote $s_1 = 2^{\frac{m}{3}} + 2^{\frac{km}{3}}$ and $s_2 = 2^{\frac{2m}{3}} + 2^{\frac{(k+1)m}{3}} = 2^{\frac{m}{3}} s_1$. By Lemma 2, it suffices to prove that for each $d \in \mathcal{J}$, the equation

$$(x + \delta)^{2^m s_1} + (x + \delta)^{s_1} + (x + \delta)^{2^m s_2} + (x + \delta)^{s_2} = x + d \quad (38)$$

has exactly one solution in $\mathcal{J}$. Raising both sides of (38) to the power $2^{\frac{m}{3}}$ and $2^{\frac{2m}{3}}$ respectively, we have

$$(x + \delta)^{2^m s_2} + (x + \delta)^{s_2} + (x + \delta)^{2^{\frac{4m}{3}} s_2} + (x + \delta)^{2^{\frac{m}{3}} s_2} = x^{2^{\frac{m}{3}}} + d^{2^{\frac{m}{3}}}, \quad (39)$$

and

$$(x + \delta)^{2^{\frac{4m}{3}} s_2} + (x + \delta)^{2^{\frac{m}{3}} s_2} + (x + \delta)^{s_1} + (x + \delta)^{2^m s_1} = x^{2^{\frac{2m}{3}}} + d^{2^{\frac{2m}{3}}}. \quad (40)$$

It follows from (38), (39) and (40) that

$$(x + d)^{2^{\frac{2m}{3}}} + (x + d)^{2^{\frac{m}{3}}} + x + d = 0. \quad (41)$$

Denote $\alpha = x + d$, then (41) can be rewritten as

$$\alpha^{2^{\frac{2m}{3}}} + \alpha^{2^{\frac{m}{3}}} + \alpha = 0. \quad (42)$$

Thus, $\alpha^{2^m} = \alpha$ due to $(\alpha^{2^{\frac{2m}{3}}} + \alpha^{2^{\frac{m}{3}}} + \alpha)^{2^{\frac{m}{3}}} = 0 = \alpha^{2^{\frac{2m}{3}}} + \alpha^{2^{\frac{m}{3}}} + \alpha$.

(i) For the case $k \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$, let $k = 3t$ for an integer $t \geq 0$. Since $d \in \mathcal{J}$, we have $d^{2^m} = d$ and then $\text{Tr}_{m/3}^{2m}(d) = (d^{2^m} + d)^{2^{\frac{2m}{3}}} + (d^{2^m} + d)^{2^{\frac{m}{3}}} + (d^{2^m} + d) = 0$. Substituting x with $\alpha + d$

on the left side of (38), by $\text{Tr}_{m/3}^{2m}(d) = 0$, $\alpha^{2^m} = \alpha$ and (42), we have

$$\begin{aligned}
& (x + \delta)^{2^m s_1} + (x + \delta)^{s_1} + (x + \delta)^{2^m s_2} + (x + \delta)^{s_2} \\
= & (\alpha + d + \delta)^{2^m \left(2^{\frac{m}{3}} + 2^{\frac{km}{3}}\right)} + (\alpha + d + \delta)^{2^{\frac{m}{3}} + 2^{\frac{km}{3}}} + (\alpha + d + \delta)^{2^m \left(2^{\frac{2m}{3}} + 2^{\frac{(k+1)m}{3}}\right)} \\
& + (\alpha + d + \delta)^{2^{\frac{2m}{3}} + 2^{\frac{(k+1)m}{3}}} \\
= & (\alpha + d + \delta)^{2^{\frac{4m}{3}}} (\alpha + d + \delta)^{2^{(t+1)m}} + (\alpha + d + \delta)^{2^{\frac{m}{3}}} (\alpha + d + \delta)^{2^{tm}} \\
& + (\alpha + d + \delta)^{2^{\frac{5m}{3}}} (\alpha + d + \delta)^{2^{\frac{4m}{3} + tm}} + (\alpha + d + \delta)^{2^{\frac{2m}{3}}} (\alpha + d + \delta)^{2^{\frac{m}{3} + tm}} \\
= & \left(\alpha^{2^{\frac{m}{3}}} + (d + \delta)^{2^{\frac{4m}{3}}}\right) \left(\alpha + (d + \delta)^{2^{(t+1)m}}\right) + \left(\alpha^{2^{\frac{m}{3}}} + (d + \delta)^{2^{\frac{m}{3}}}\right) \left(\alpha + (d + \delta)^{2^{tm}}\right) \\
& + \left(\alpha^{2^{\frac{2m}{3}}} + (d + \delta)^{2^{\frac{5m}{3}}}\right) \left(\alpha^{2^{\frac{m}{3}}} + (d + \delta)^{2^{\frac{4m}{3} + tm}}\right) \\
& + \left(\alpha^{2^{\frac{2m}{3}}} + (d + \delta)^{2^{\frac{2m}{3}}}\right) \left(\alpha^{2^{\frac{m}{3}}} + (d + \delta)^{2^{\frac{m}{3} + tm}}\right) \\
= & \text{Tr}_{m/3}^{2m}(d + \delta) \alpha^{2^{\frac{m}{3}}} + (d + \delta)^{2^{\frac{m}{3} + 2^{tm}}} + (d + \delta)^{2^{\frac{m}{3}}} \left(2^{\frac{m}{3}} + 2^{tm}\right) + (d + \delta)^{2^m} \left(2^{\frac{m}{3}} + 2^{tm}\right) \\
& + (d + \delta)^{2^{\frac{4m}{3}}} \left(2^{\frac{m}{3}} + 2^{tm}\right) \\
= & \text{Tr}_{m/3}^{2m}(\delta) \alpha^{2^{\frac{m}{3}}} + (d + \delta)^{2^{\frac{m}{3} + 2^{tm}}} + (d + \delta)^{2^{\frac{m}{3}}} \left(2^{\frac{m}{3}} + 2^{tm}\right) + (d + \delta)^{2^m} \left(2^{\frac{m}{3}} + 2^{tm}\right) \\
& + (d + \delta)^{2^{\frac{4m}{3}}} \left(2^{\frac{m}{3}} + 2^{tm}\right).
\end{aligned}$$

Denote $\beta = \text{Tr}_{m/3}^{2m}(\delta)$ and $\gamma = (d + \delta)^{2^{\frac{m}{3}} + 2^{tm}} + (d + \delta)^{2^{\frac{m}{3}}} \left(2^{\frac{m}{3}} + 2^{tm}\right) + (d + \delta)^{2^m} \left(2^{\frac{m}{3}} + 2^{tm}\right) + (d + \delta)^{2^{\frac{4m}{3}}} \left(2^{\frac{m}{3}} + 2^{tm}\right)$, then we have $\beta^{2^{\frac{m}{3}}} = \beta$ and $\gamma^{2^m} = \gamma$. Thus Equation (38) can be written as

$$\beta \alpha^{2^{\frac{m}{3}}} + \alpha + \gamma = 0. \quad (43)$$

It follows from (42) and (43) that

$$\left(\beta \alpha^{2^{\frac{m}{3}}} + \alpha + \gamma\right)^{2^{\frac{m}{3}}} = \beta \left(\alpha^{2^{\frac{2m}{3}}} + \alpha^{2^{\frac{m}{3}}} + \alpha\right)$$

and then

$$(\beta + 1) \alpha^{2^{\frac{m}{3}}} + \beta \alpha + \gamma^{2^{\frac{m}{3}}} = 0. \quad (44)$$

Eliminating the term $\alpha^{2^{\frac{m}{3}}}$ in (43) and (44) gives

$$(\beta^2 + \beta + 1) \alpha = (\beta + 1) \gamma + \beta \gamma^{2^{\frac{m}{3}}}.$$

We claim that $\beta^2 + \beta + 1 \neq 0$. Otherwise, β is a root of $x^2 + x + 1 = 0$. Since $x^2 + x + 1 = 0$ is irreducible in $\mathbb{F}_2$, $\beta \in \mathbb{F}_{2^2}$ and $\beta \notin \mathbb{F}_2$, i.e., $\beta^4 = \beta \neq \beta^2$. Note that $\frac{m}{3}$ is odd, then

$$\beta^{2^{\frac{m}{3}}} = \beta^{2^{2 \cdot \frac{1}{2}(\frac{m}{3}-1)+1}} = \beta^{4^{\frac{1}{2}(\frac{m}{3}-1)} \cdot 2} = \beta^2 \neq \beta,$$

which contradicts with $\beta \in \mathbb{F}_{2^{\frac{m}{3}}}$. Thus $\beta^2 + \beta + 1 \neq 0$ and then $\alpha = (\beta^2 + \beta + 1)^{-1} \left((\beta + 1)\gamma + \beta\gamma^2 \right)^{\frac{m}{3}}$. Therefore, $x = (\beta^2 + \beta + 1)^{-1} \left((\beta + 1)\gamma + \beta\gamma^2 \right)^{\frac{m}{3}} + d$ is the unique solution of (38) in $\mathcal{J}$.

(ii) For the case $k \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, let $k = 1 + 3t$ for an integer $t \geq 0$. In this case, $s_1 = 2^{\frac{m}{3}} + 2^{(\frac{1}{3}+t)m}$ and $s_2 = 2^{\frac{2m}{3}} + 2^{(\frac{2}{3}+t)m}$.

If $2|t$, then $s_1 \equiv 2^{\frac{m}{3}+1} \pmod{2^{2m} - 1}$ and $s_2 \equiv 2^{\frac{2m}{3}+1} \pmod{2^{2m} - 1}$. Equation (38) is equivalent to

$$x + \delta^2 \delta^{\frac{5m}{3}+1} + \delta^2 \delta^{\frac{4m}{3}+1} + \delta^2 \delta^{\frac{2m}{3}+1} + \delta^2 \delta^{\frac{m}{3}+1} = d,$$

i.e., $x = \delta^2 \delta^{\frac{5m}{3}+1} + \delta^2 \delta^{\frac{4m}{3}+1} + \delta^2 \delta^{\frac{2m}{3}+1} + \delta^2 \delta^{\frac{m}{3}+1} + d$ is its unique solution.

If $2 \nmid t$, then $s_1 \equiv s_1 2^m \pmod{2^{2m} - 1}$ and $s_2 \equiv s_2 2^m \pmod{2^{2m} - 1}$. Thus, $x = d$ is the unique solution of (38) in $\mathcal{J}$.

(iii) For the case $k \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$, let $k = 3t + 2$ for an integer $t \geq 0$. Substituting x with $\alpha + d$ on the left side of (38), we have

$$\begin{aligned} & (x + \delta)^{s_1} + (x + \delta)^{2^m s_1} + (x + \delta)^{s_2} + (x + \delta)^{2^m s_2} \\ = & (\alpha + d + \delta)^{2^m \left(2^{\frac{m}{3} + 2\frac{km}{3}} \right)} + (\alpha + d + \delta)^{2^{\frac{m}{3} + 2\frac{km}{3}}} + (\alpha + d + \delta)^{2^m \left(2^{\frac{2m}{3} + 2\frac{(k+1)m}{3}} \right)} \\ & + (\alpha + d + \delta)^{2^{\frac{2m}{3} + 2\frac{(k+1)m}{3}}} \\ = & (\alpha + d + \delta)^{2^{\frac{4m}{3}}} (\alpha + d + \delta)^{2^{(t+\frac{5}{3})m}} + (\alpha + d + \delta)^{2^{\frac{m}{3}}} (\alpha + d + \delta)^{2^{(t+\frac{2}{3})m}} \\ & + (\alpha + d + \delta)^{2^{\frac{5m}{3}}} (\alpha + d + \delta)^{2^{tm}} + (\alpha + d + \delta)^{2^{\frac{2m}{3}}} (\alpha + d + \delta)^{2^{(t+1)m}} \\ = & \text{Tr}_{m/3}^{2m}(d + \delta) \alpha^2 \delta^{\frac{2m}{3}} + (d + \delta)^{2^{\frac{m}{3} + 2\frac{2m}{3} + tm}} + (d + \delta)^{2^{\frac{m}{3}}} \left(2^{\frac{m}{3} + 2\frac{2m}{3} + tm} \right) \\ & + (d + \delta)^{2^m \left(2^{\frac{m}{3} + 2\frac{2m}{3} + tm} \right)} + (d + \delta)^{2^{\frac{4m}{3}}} \left(2^{\frac{m}{3} + 2\frac{2m}{3} + tm} \right) \\ = & \text{Tr}_{m/3}^{2m}(\delta) \alpha^2 \delta^{\frac{2m}{3}} + (d + \delta)^{2^{\frac{m}{3} + 2\frac{2m}{3} + tm}} + (d + \delta)^{2^{\frac{m}{3}}} \left(2^{\frac{m}{3} + 2\frac{2m}{3} + tm} \right) + (d + \delta)^{2^m \left(2^{\frac{m}{3} + 2\frac{2m}{3} + tm} \right)} \\ & + (d + \delta)^{2^{\frac{4m}{3}}} \left(2^{\frac{m}{3} + 2\frac{2m}{3} + tm} \right) \\ = & \beta \alpha^2 \delta^{\frac{2m}{3}} + \mu \end{aligned}$$

due to $\text{Tr}_{m/3}^{2m}(d) = 0$, $\alpha^{2^m} = \alpha$ and (42). Denote $\beta = \text{Tr}_{m/3}^{2m}(\delta)$ and $\mu = (d + \delta)^{2^{\frac{m}{3} + 2\frac{2m}{3} + tm}} + (d + \delta)^{2^{\frac{m}{3}}} \left(2^{\frac{m}{3} + 2\frac{2m}{3} + tm} \right) + (d + \delta)^{2^m \left(2^{\frac{m}{3} + 2\frac{2m}{3} + tm} \right)} + (d + \delta)^{2^{\frac{4m}{3}}} \left(2^{\frac{m}{3} + 2\frac{2m}{3} + tm} \right)$, we have $\beta^2 \delta^{\frac{m}{3}} = \beta$ and $\mu^{2^m} = \mu$. Then (38) is equivalent to

$$\beta \alpha^2 \delta^{\frac{2m}{3}} + \alpha + \mu = 0. \quad (45)$$

According to (42) and (45), we have

$$\beta \left(\alpha^2 \delta^{\frac{2m}{3}} + \alpha^2 \delta^{\frac{m}{3}} + \alpha \right) = \beta \alpha^2 \delta^{\frac{2m}{3}} + \alpha + \mu,$$

i.e.,

$$\beta\alpha^{2\frac{m}{3}} + (\beta + 1)\alpha + \mu = 0. \quad (46)$$

It follows from (42) and (46) that

$$\beta \left(\alpha^{2\frac{2m}{3}} + \alpha^{2\frac{m}{3}} + \alpha \right) = \left(\beta\alpha^{2\frac{m}{3}} + (\beta + 1)\alpha + \mu \right)^{2\frac{m}{3}},$$

which implies

$$\alpha^{2\frac{m}{3}} + \beta\alpha + \mu^{2\frac{m}{3}} = 0. \quad (47)$$

Eliminating the term $\beta\alpha^{2\frac{2m}{3}}$ in (46) and (47), we have

$$(\beta^2 + \beta + 1)\alpha = \beta\mu^{2\frac{m}{3}} + \mu.$$

Similarly as in Case (i), we can prove that $\beta^2 + \beta + 1 \neq 0$ since $\frac{m}{3}$ is odd. Therefore, $\alpha = (\beta^2 + \beta + 1)^{-1} \left(\beta\mu^{2\frac{m}{3}} + \mu \right)$. As a consequence, $x = (\beta^2 + \beta + 1)^{-1} \left(\beta\mu^{2\frac{m}{3}} + \mu \right) + d$ is the unique solution of (38) in $\mathcal{J}$. $\square$

5 Other PPs $f(x)$ over $\mathbb{F}_{p^n}$

In this section, we construct three classes of permutation polynomials of the form as in (2) over $\mathbb{F}_{p^n}$ with $p \in \{2, 3\}$. The construction is different from those in Sections 3 and 4.

Proposition 15. *For positive integers m, n with $2|n, m|n$, and an element $\delta \in \mathbb{F}_{2^n}$, the polynomial*

$$f(x) = (x^{2^m} + x + \delta)^{\frac{2^n-1}{3}+2jm} + (x^{2^m} + x + \delta)^{\frac{2(2^n-1)}{3}+2jm} + x$$

is a permutation of $\mathbb{F}_{2^n}$, where $j \in \{0, \frac{n}{m} - 1\}$.

Proof. We only give the proof for the case $j = 0$ since the other case can be proved similarly. By Lemma 2, it suffices to prove that for any $d \in \mathcal{J}$, the equation

$$(x + \delta)^{2^m \left(\frac{2^n-1}{3} + 1 \right)} + (x + \delta)^{\frac{2^n-1}{3} + 1} + (x + \delta)^{2^m \left(\frac{2(2^n-1)}{3} + 1 \right)} + (x + \delta)^{\frac{2(2^n-1)}{3} + 1} = x + d \quad (48)$$

has a unique solution in $\mathcal{J}$. The left side of (48) is

$$\begin{aligned} & (x + \delta)^{2^m \left(\frac{2^n-1}{3} + 1 \right)} + (x + \delta)^{\frac{2^n-1}{3} + 1} + (x + \delta)^{2^m \left(\frac{2(2^n-1)}{3} + 1 \right)} + (x + \delta)^{\frac{2(2^n-1)}{3} + 1} \\ &= (x + \delta)^{2^m} \left((x + \delta)^{\frac{2^n-1}{3}} + (x + \delta)^{\frac{2(2^n-1)}{3}} \right)^{2^m} + (x + \delta) \left((x + \delta)^{\frac{2^n-1}{3}} + (x + \delta)^{\frac{2(2^n-1)}{3}} \right) \\ &= ((x + \delta)^{2^m} + x + \delta) \left((x + \delta)^{\frac{2^n-1}{3}} + (x + \delta)^{\frac{2(2^n-1)}{3}} \right) \\ &= (x^{2^m} + x + \delta^{2^m} + \delta) \left((x + \delta)^{\frac{2^n-1}{3}} + (x + \delta)^{\frac{2(2^n-1)}{3}} \right), \end{aligned}$$

where the second equal sign holds since

$$(x + \delta)^{\frac{2^n - 1}{3}} + (x + \delta)^{\frac{2(2^n - 1)}{3}} = \left((x + \delta)^{\frac{2^n - 1}{3}} + (x + \delta)^{\frac{2(2^n - 1)}{3}} \right)^2$$

for a positive integer i . So (48) is equivalent to

$$(x^{2^m} + x + \delta^{2^m} + \delta) \left((x + \delta)^{\frac{2^n - 1}{3}} + (x + \delta)^{\frac{2(2^n - 1)}{3}} \right) = x + d. \quad (49)$$

In the following, we discuss the solutions of (49) in the following three cases.

(1) $d = \delta$.

If $x^{2^m} + x + \delta^{2^m} + \delta = 0$, then $x = d$. Otherwise, dividing both sides of (49) by $x^{2^m} + x + \delta^{2^m} + \delta$, we have

$$(x + \delta)^{\frac{2^n - 1}{3}} + (x + \delta)^{\frac{2(2^n - 1)}{3}} = \frac{x + d}{x^{2^m} + x + \delta^{2^m} + \delta}$$

and then

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{x + d}{x^{2^m} + x + \delta^{2^m} + \delta} &= (x + \delta)^{\frac{2^n - 1}{3}} + (x + \delta)^{\frac{2(2^n - 1)}{3}} \\ &= \left((x + \delta)^{\frac{2^n - 1}{3}} + (x + \delta)^{\frac{2(2^n - 1)}{3}} \right)^2 \\ &= \left(\frac{x + d}{x^{2^m} + x + \delta^{2^m} + \delta} \right)^2, \end{aligned}$$

i.e., $\left(\frac{x + d}{x^{2^m} + x + \delta^{2^m} + \delta} \right)^2 = \frac{x + d}{x^{2^m} + x + \delta^{2^m} + \delta}$, which implies $x = (\delta^{2^m} + \delta + d)^{2^{n-m}}$ or $x = d$. Since $d = \delta$, we have $x = (\delta^{2^m} + \delta + d)^{2^{n-m}} = \delta = d$. Thus, $x = d$ is the unique solution.

(2) $d \neq \delta$ and $d^{2^m} + d + \delta^{2^m} + \delta = 0$.

If $x^{2^m} + x + \delta^{2^m} + \delta = 0$, then $x = d$ by (49). Otherwise, similarly as in Case (1), we have $x = (\delta^{2^m} + \delta + d)^{2^{n-m}}$ or $x = d$. We claim that $x = d$. Otherwise,

$$x^{2^m} + x + \delta^{2^m} + \delta = \delta^{2^m} + \delta + d + (\delta^{2^m} + \delta + d)^{2^{n-m}} + \delta^{2^m} + \delta \neq 0$$

and then

$$(\delta^{2^m} + \delta + d)^{2^{n-m}} + d \neq 0,$$

i.e., $d^{2^m} + d + \delta^{2^m} + \delta \neq 0$. This contradicts with the assumption $d^{2^m} + d + \delta^{2^m} + \delta = 0$.

(3) $d \neq \delta$ and $d^{2^m} + d + \delta^{2^m} + \delta \neq 0$.

If $x^{2^m} + x + \delta^{2^m} + \delta = 0$, we have $x = d$ and then $d^{2^m} + d + \delta^{2^m} + \delta = 0$. This contradicts with the assumption $d^{2^m} + d + \delta^{2^m} + \delta \neq 0$.

If $x^{2^m} + x + \delta^{2^m} + \delta \neq 0$, similarly as in Case (1), we have $x = (\delta^{2^m} + \delta + d)^{2^{n-m}}$ or $x = d$. We claim that $x = (\delta^{2^m} + \delta + d)^{2^{n-m}}$ and $x = d$ can not hold simultaneously. Otherwise, substituting

x with $(\delta^{2^m} + \delta + d)^{2^{n-m}}$ and d on both sides of (49) respectively, we have

$$\begin{cases} \left((\delta^{2^m} + \delta + d)^{2^{n-m}} + d \right) \left((\delta^{2^m} + \delta + d)^{2^{n-m}} + \delta \right)^{\frac{(2^n-1)}{3}} + \left((\delta^{2^m} + \delta + d)^{2^{n-m}} + \delta \right)^{\frac{2(2^n-1)}{3}} \\ = (\delta^{2^m} + \delta + d)^{2^{n-m}} + d, \\ (d^{2^m} + d + \delta^{2^m} + \delta) \left((d + \delta)^{\frac{(2^n-1)}{3}} + (d + \delta)^{\frac{2(2^n-1)}{3}} \right) = 0. \end{cases}$$

Since $d^{2^m} + d + \delta^{2^m} + \delta \neq 0$, we have $(\delta^{2^m} + \delta + d)^{2^{n-m}} + d = (d^{2^m} + d + \delta^{2^m} + \delta)^{2^{n-m}} \neq 0$. Then

$$\begin{cases} ((\delta^{2^m} + \delta + d)^{2^{n-m}} + \delta)^{\frac{(2^n-1)}{3}} + ((\delta^{2^m} + \delta + d)^{2^{n-m}} + \delta)^{\frac{2(2^n-1)}{3}} = 1, \\ (d + \delta)^{\frac{(2^n-1)}{3}} + (d + \delta)^{\frac{2(2^n-1)}{3}} = 0. \end{cases}$$

Thus, we have

$$\begin{aligned} 1 &= ((\delta^{2^m} + \delta + d)^{2^{n-m}} + \delta)^{\frac{(2^n-1)}{3}} + ((\delta^{2^m} + \delta + d)^{2^{n-m}} + \delta)^{\frac{2(2^n-1)}{3}} \\ &= \left(((\delta^{2^m} + \delta + d)^{2^{n-m}} + \delta)^{\frac{(2^n-1)}{3}} + ((\delta^{2^m} + \delta + d)^{2^{n-m}} + \delta)^{\frac{2(2^n-1)}{3}} \right)^{2^m} \\ &= (d + \delta)^{\frac{(2^n-1)}{3}} + (d + \delta)^{\frac{2(2^n-1)}{3}} \\ &= 0, \end{aligned}$$

which is a contradiction. Hence (48) has at most one solution in $\mathcal{J}$. $\square$

Proposition 16. *Let m, i be two nonnegative integers with $m > 0$, $i \in \{0, 1\}$, and a fixed $\delta \in \mathbb{F}_{3^{2m}}$, the polynomial*

$$f(x) = (x^{3^m} - x + \delta)^{3^m+2} + (x^{3^m} - x + \delta)^{2 \cdot 3^{im}} + x$$

is a permutation of $\mathbb{F}_{3^{2m}}$.

Proof. We only prove the case $i = 1$ since the other case can be shown in a similar way. By Lemma 2, it suffices to prove that for each $d \in \mathcal{J}$ defined in (3), the equation

$$\begin{aligned} & (x + \delta)^{3^m(3^m+2)} - (x + \delta)^{3^m+2} + (x + \delta)^{2 \cdot 3^{2m}} - (x + \delta)^{2 \cdot 3^m} + x \\ &= (x + \delta)^{2 \cdot 3^m} (x + \delta) - (x + \delta)^{3^m} (x + \delta)^2 + (x + \delta)^2 - (x + \delta)^{2 \cdot 3^m} + x \\ &= (x - \delta^{3^m})^2 (x + \delta) - (-x + \delta^{3^m}) (x + \delta)^2 + (x + \delta)^2 - (x - \delta^{3^m})^2 + x \\ &= (x^2 + \delta^{3^m} x + \delta^{2 \cdot 3^m}) (x + \delta) - (-x + \delta^{3^m}) (x^2 - \delta x + \delta^2) + (x^2 - \delta x + \delta^2) - \\ & \quad (x^2 + \delta^{3^m} x + \delta^{2 \cdot 3^m}) + x \\ &= -x^3 + ((\delta^{3^m} + \delta)^2 + 2(\delta^{3^m} + \delta) + 1) x + \delta^{2 \cdot 3^m+1} - \delta^{3^m+2} + \delta^2 - \delta^{2 \cdot 3^m} \\ &= -x^3 + (\text{Tr}_m^{3^m}(\delta) + 1)^2 x + \delta^{2 \cdot 3^m+1} - \delta^{3^m+2} + \delta^2 - \delta^{2 \cdot 3^m} \\ &= d \end{aligned}$$

has at most one solution in $\mathcal{J}$, where the second equal sign holds due to (4). The above equation can be written as

$$x^3 - (\text{Tr}_m^{3m}(\delta) + 1)^2 x = \delta^{2 \cdot 3^m + 1} - \delta^{3^m + 2} + \delta^2 - \delta^{2 \cdot 3^m} - d. \quad (50)$$

By Lemma 3, (50) has at most one solution in $\mathcal{J}$. $\square$

Proposition 17. *For a positive integer m and a fixed $\delta \in \mathbb{F}_{3^{2m}}$, the polynomial*

$$f(x) = (x^{3^m} - x + \delta)^{\frac{3^{2m}+1}{2}} + (x^{3^m} - x + \delta)^{\frac{3^{2m}+3^m}{2}} + x$$

is a permutation of $\mathbb{F}_{3^{2m}}$.

Proof. By Lemma 2, it suffices to prove that for any $d \in \mathcal{J}$, the equation

$$(x + \delta)^{\frac{3^m(3^{2m}+1)}{2}} - (x + \delta)^{\frac{3^{2m}+1}{2}} + (x + \delta)^{\frac{3^m(3^{2m}+3^m)}{2}} - (x + \delta)^{\frac{3^{2m}+3^m}{2}} + x = d \quad (51)$$

has at most one solution in $\mathcal{J}$.

If $x = -\delta$, then $x = -\delta = d$, as desired. In the sequel, suppose that $x \neq -\delta$. Note that $(x + \delta)^{\frac{3^{2m}-1}{2}} = \pm 1$. We investigate (51) in two cases in terms of the value of $(x + \delta)^{\frac{3^{2m}-1}{2}}$.

(1) $(x + \delta)^{\frac{3^{2m}-1}{2}} = 1$. Then (51) becomes

$$x = \delta^{3^m} - \delta - d,$$

which implies $(\delta^{3^m} - d)^{\frac{3^{2m}-1}{2}} = (\delta^{3^m} + d^{3^m})^{\frac{3^{2m}-1}{2}} = (\delta + d)^{\frac{3^{2m}-1}{2}} = 1$.

(2) $(x + \delta)^{\frac{3^{2m}-1}{2}} = -1$. Then (51) becomes

$$(x + \delta)^{\frac{3^m+1}{2}} = -\delta^{3^m} + \delta - d. \quad (52)$$

Thus, we get $(x + \delta)^{3^m+1} = (\delta^{3^m} - \delta + d)^2$, which is equivalent to

$$x^2 - (\delta^{3^m} - \delta)x + (\delta^{3^m} - \delta + d)^2 - \delta^{3^m+1} = 0. \quad (53)$$

By computing, we get that $x_1 = -\delta^{3^m} + \delta - (\delta + d)^{\frac{3^m+1}{2}}$, $x_2 = -\delta^{3^m} + \delta + (\delta + d)^{\frac{3^m+1}{2}}$ are two solutions of (53). In the following, we prove that (52) has at most one solution in $\mathcal{J}$. Since any solution of (52) is also a solution to (53), suppose that (52) has two solutions x_1, x_2 in $\mathcal{J}$. Then

$$x_1 + \delta = \delta^{3^m} - x_2 = (x_2 + \delta)^{3^m},$$

where the second equal sign holds due to $\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(x_2) = 0$. It follows that

$$(x_1 + \delta)^{\frac{3^m+1}{2}} = (x_2 + \delta)^{\frac{3^m(3^m+1)}{2}} = (x_2 + \delta)^{\frac{3^{2m}-1}{2} + \frac{3^m+1}{2}} = -(x_2 + \delta)^{\frac{3^m+1}{2}}.$$

On the other hand, by (52), $(x_1 + \delta)^{\frac{3^m+1}{2}} = (x_2 + \delta)^{\frac{3^m+1}{2}} = -\delta^{3^m} + \delta - d$. This implies that $(x_1 + \delta)^{\frac{3^m+1}{2}} = 0$, which contradicts the fact that $(x_1 + \delta)^{\frac{3^{2m}-1}{2}} = -1$. Hence (52) has at most one solution in $\mathcal{J}$, which is denoted as x_1 in the following.

Now we show that (51) has at most one solution in $\mathcal{J}$. Recall that the solutions we obtained in Cases 1 and 2 are $\delta^{3^m} - \delta - d$ and x_1 respectively. If $d = -\delta$, then $x_1 = \delta^{3^m} - \delta - d = -\delta$. Thus, $x = -\delta$ is the unique solution of (51). If $d \neq -\delta$, we claim that $x = x_1$ and $x = \delta^{3^m} - \delta - d$ can not hold simultaneously. Otherwise,

$$\begin{aligned} (x_1 + \delta)^{3^m} &= (-\delta^{3^m} - \delta - (\delta + d)^{\frac{3^m+1}{2}})^{3^m} \\ &= -\delta^{3^m} - \delta - (\delta + d)^{\frac{3^{2m}-1}{2} + \frac{3^m+1}{2}} \\ &= x_1 + \delta, \end{aligned}$$

where the second equal sign holds due to $(\delta + d)^{\frac{3^{2m}-1}{2}} = 1$ in Case 1. Then $(x_1 + \delta)^{\frac{3^{2m}-1}{2}} = (x_1 + \delta)^{(3^m-1) \cdot \frac{3^m+1}{2}} = 1$. This contradicts the assumption $(x_1 + \delta)^{\frac{3^{2m}-1}{2}} = -1$ in Case 2. Therefore, (51) has at most one solution in $\mathcal{J}$. $\square$

To end this section, we summarize known permutation polynomials having the form as in (2) in Tables 3 and 4.

6 Acknowledgments

The work of X. Zeng was supported by the National Natural Science Foundation of China (No. 61672212). The work of L. Li was supported by the National Natural Science Foundation of China (No. 61702166) and National Natural Science Foundation of Hubei Province of China (No. 2017CFB143). C. Li was supported by European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. H2020-MSCA-ITN-2014-643161 ECRYPT-NET.

References

- [1] A. Akbary, D. Ghioca, Q. Wang, On constructing permutations of finite fields, *Finite Fields Appl.* 17(1) (2011) 51-67.
- [2] N. Cepak, P. Charpin, E. Pasalic, Permutations via linear translators, *Finite Fields Appl.* 45 (2017) 19-42.
- [3] T. Helleseht, V. Zinoviev, New Kloosterman sums identities over $\mathbb{F}_{2^m}$ for all m , *Finite Fields Appl.* 9(2) (2003) 187-193.

Table 3: Known permutation polynomials $(x^{2^m} + x + \delta)^{s_1} + (x^{2^m} + x + \delta)^{s_2} + x$ over $\mathbb{F}_{2^n}$

Values of m, n, s_1 and s_2	Conditions on δ	Reference
$n = 2m, s_1 = 2^m + 1$ and $s_2 = 2^{m+1} - 1$	all	[16]
$n = 2m, s_1 = 2 - 2^m$ and $s_2 = 3 - 2^{m+1}$	all	[16]
$n = 3m, m = 2, s_1 = 2^{2^m} + 1$ and $s_2 = 2^m + 1$	$\text{Tr}_1^n(\delta) = 1$	[16]
n is even, $m = 2, s_1 = -4$ and $s_2 = -2$	$\text{Tr}_1^n(\delta) = 1$	[16]
$n \equiv 2 \pmod{4}, m = 2, s_1 = \frac{2^n+1}{5}$ and $s_2 = \frac{3 \cdot 2^n - 2}{5}$	all	[16]
$n \equiv 1 \pmod{3}, n$ is even, $m = 2, s_1 = \frac{2^{n+2}-1}{7}$ and $s_2 = \frac{6 \cdot 2^n - 5}{7}$	all	[16]
n is even, $m = 2, s_1 = \frac{2^{n-1}+1}{3}$ and $s_2 = \frac{5 \cdot 2^{n-1}-1}{3}$	all	[16]
$n = 2m, s_2 = 2^m s_1$ and s_1 is a positive integer	all	This paper
$n = 2m, s_1 = \frac{i(2^{2^m}-1)}{3} + 1, s_2 = \frac{i(2^{2^m}-1)}{3} + 2^m$ and i is a nonnegative integer	all	This paper
$n = 2m, s_1 = 2^{m+i} + 2^j, s_2 = 2^{m+i} + 2^{m+j}$ and i, j are nonnegative integers	all	This paper
$n = 2m, m$ is even, $s_1 = 2^{\frac{jm}{2^i}} + 2^{\frac{j}{2^i} + \frac{km}{2}}$, $s_2 = 2^{(\frac{j}{2^i} + \frac{1}{2})m} + 2^{\frac{jm}{2^i} + \frac{(k+1)m}{2}}$ and i, j, k are nonnegative integers with $2^i \mid jm$	all	This paper
$n = 2m, s_1 = 2^{\frac{im}{3}} + 2^{\frac{km}{3}}, s_2 = 2^{\frac{2im}{3}} + 2^{\frac{(k+i)m}{3}}$ and the parameters k, i, m are mentioned in Proposition 14	all	This paper
$n = 3m, s_2 = 2^m s_1, s_1 \in \{2^m + 1, 2^{(i+1)m-1} + 2^{im-1}\}, \gcd(im + 1, 3m) = 1$ and $i \in \{1, 2\}$	all	This paper
$n = 3m, s_1 = 2^{jm+i} + 2^{2m}, s_2 = 2^{(j+2)m+i} + 1, \gcd(jm + i, 3m) = 1,$ $j \in \{0, 1, 2\}$ and i is a positive integer	all	This paper
n is even, $m \mid n, s_1 = \frac{2^n-1}{3} + 2^{jm}, s_2 = \frac{2(2^n-1)}{3} + 2^{jm}$ and $j \in \{0, \frac{n}{m} - 1\}$	all	This paper
$n = 3m, s_1 = 2^{2m+1} + 2^m$ and $s_2 = 2^{2m} + 2^{m+1}$	$\text{Tr}_m^{3m}(\delta) = 0$	This paper
$m \mid n, s_1 = \frac{j(2^n-1)}{2^m-1}, s_2$ is a positive integer such that $(x^{2^m} + x + \delta)^{s_2} + x$ permutes $\mathbb{F}_{2^n}$ and j is a positive integer	all	This paper

- [4] N. Li, T. Helleseht, X. Tang, Further results on a class of permutation polynomials over finite fields, *Finite Fields Appl.* 22 (2013) 16-23.
- [5] G.L. Mullen, D. Panario (eds.), *Handbook of Finite Fields*, CRC Press, Boca Raton, 2013.
- [6] Z. Tu, X. Zeng, Y. Jiang, Two classes of permutation polynomials having the form $(x^{2^m} + x + \delta)^s + x$, *Finite Fields Appl.* 31 (2015) 12-24.
- [7] Z. Tu, X. Zeng, C. Li, T. Helleseht, Permutation polynomials of the form $(x^{p^m} - x + \delta)^s + L(x)$ over the finite field $\mathbb{F}_{p^{2m}}$ of odd characteristic, *Finite Fields Appl.* 34 (2015) 20-35.
- [8] L. Wang, B. Wu, Z. Liu, Further results on permutation polynomials of the form $(x^{p^m} - x + \delta)^s + L(x)$ over $\mathbb{F}_{p^{2m}}$, *Finite Fields Appl.* 44 (2017) 92-112.
- [9] J. Yuan, C. Ding, Four classes of permutation polynomials of $\mathbb{F}_{2^m}$, *Finite Fields Appl.* 13(4) (2007) 869-876.
- [10] J. Yuan, C. Ding, H. Wang, J. Pieprzyk, Permutation polynomials of the form $(x^p - x + \delta)^s + L(x)$, *Finite Fields Appl.* 14(2) (2008) 482-493.

Table 4: Known permutation polynomials $(x^{p^m} - x + \delta)^{s_1} + (x^{p^m} - x + \delta)^{s_2} + x$ over $\mathbb{F}_{p^n}$ with odd prime p

Values of m, n, s_1 and s_2	Conditions on δ	Reference
$n = 2m, s_2 = p^m s_1$ and s_1 is a positive integer	all	This paper
$n = 2m, m$ is even, $s_1 = \frac{i(p^{2m}-1)}{p^2-1} + 1, s_2 = \frac{i(p^{2m}-1)}{p^2-1} + p^m$ and i is a nonnegative integer	all	This paper
$n = 2m, p = 3, s_1 = 2 \cdot 3^{m+i} + 3^j, s_2 = 2 \cdot 3^{m+i} + 3^{m+j}, \gcd(i, 2m) = 1$ and i, j are nonnegative integers	all	This paper
$n = 2m, s_1 = \frac{3^{2m}+1}{2}$ and $s_2 = \frac{3^{2m}+3^m}{2}$	all	This paper
$n = 2m, p = 3, s_1 = 3^m + 4$ and $s_2 = 5$	$1 - [\text{Tr}_m^{2m}(\delta)]^4$ is a square of $\mathbb{F}_{3^m}$	This paper
$n = 3m, p = 3, s_1 = \frac{3^{3m}-1}{2} + 1$ and $s_2 = \frac{3^{3m}-1}{2} + 3^{2m}$	all	This paper
$n = 3m, p = 3, s_1 = 3^m + 2, s_2 = 2 \cdot 3^{im}$ and $i \in \{0, 1\}$	all	This paper
$n = 3m, s_1 = 2p^{2m} + p^m$ and $s_2 = p^{2m} + 2p^m$	$\text{Tr}_m^{3m}(\delta) = 0$	This paper
$n = 3m, p = 3, s_1 = \frac{3^{3m}-1}{2} + 3^{im}, s_2 = \frac{3^{3m}-1}{2} + 3^{jm}$ and $i = 0, j = 1$ or $i = 1, j = 2$	$\text{Tr}_m^{3m}(\delta) = 0$	This paper
$n = 3m, s_1 = \frac{p^{3m}-1}{2} + p^{2m} + p^m - 1$ and $s_2 = \frac{p^{3m}-1}{2} + 2p^m - 1$	$\text{Tr}_m^{3m}(\delta) = 0$	This paper
$m n, s_1 = \frac{j(p^n-1)}{p^m-1}, s_2$ is a positive integer such that $(x^{p^m} - x + \delta)^{s_2} + x$ permutes $\mathbb{F}_{p^n}$ and j is a positive integer	all	This paper

- [11] P. Yuan, C. Ding, Permutation polynomials over finite fields from a powerful lemma, *Finite Fields Appl.* 17(6) (2011) 560-574.
- [12] P. Yuan, C. Ding, Further results on permutation polynomials over finite fields, *Finite Fields Appl.* 27 (2014) 88-103.
- [13] P. Yuan, Y. Zheng, Permutation polynomials from piecewise functions, *Finite Fields Appl.* 35 (2015) 215-230.
- [14] D. Zheng, Z. Chen, More classes of permutation polynomials of the form $(x^{p^m} - x + \delta)^s + L(x)$, *Appl. Algebra Engrg. Comm. Comput.* 28(3) (2017) 215-223.
- [15] X. Zeng, X. Zhu, L. Hu, Two new permutation polynomials with the form $(x^{2^k} + x + \delta)^s + x$ over $\mathbb{F}_{2^n}$, *Appl. Algebra Engrg. Comm. Comput.* 21(2) (2010) 145-150.
- [16] X. Zeng, X. Zhu, N. Li, X. Liu, Permutation polynomials over $\mathbb{F}_{2^n}$ of the form $(x^{2^i} + x + \delta)^{s_1} + (x^{2^i} + x + \delta)^{s_2} + x$, *Finite Fields Appl.* 47 (2017) 256-268.
- [17] Z. Zha, L. Hu, Two classes of permutation polynomials over finite fields, *Finite Fields Appl.* 18(4) (2012) 781-790.
- [18] Z. Zha, L. Hu, Some classes of permutation polynomials of the form $(x^{p^m} - x + \delta)^s + x$ over $\mathbb{F}_{p^{2m}}$, *Finite Fields Appl.* 40 (2016) 150-162.